

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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TRANSITION TO PRACTICE PROGRAM EFFECTS ON CRNA/APRN SATISFACTION &
RETENTION: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

As novice certified registered nurse anesthetists (CRNAs) and other advanced practice registered nurses (APRNs) transition into independent practice, they experience increased stress and psychological challenges that may decrease job satisfaction and increase the likelihood that they leave their jobs within the first year. Retaining anesthesia providers is of paramount importance to healthcare organizations that wish to reduce operating costs and maintain patient access to care. To enhance job satisfaction and the retention of CRNAs (and other APRNs), scholars argue that new graduates may need help transitioning into the workforce through transition to practice (TTP) programs. The purpose of this DNP project was to conduct a systematic review of the literature to synthesize evidence related to the effectiveness of TTP programs and to determine which individual components are frequently included in such programs. Nine studies met inclusion criteria. Results indicate that TTP programs are associated with increased job satisfaction and retention for APRNs, and typically include components such as mentorship, didactic training, and ongoing evaluation. Findings are discussed regarding the strength of these relationships and directions for future research.

Keywords: Systematic Review, Transition to Practice (TTP), Fellowship, Advanced Practice Registered Nurse (APRN), Certified Registered Nurse Anesthetist (CRNA), Job Satisfaction, Retention

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Background

Certified Registered Nurse Anesthetists (CRNAs) provide anesthesia services to more than 50 million patients annually in the United States (U.S.) and represent over 80% of anesthesia providers in rural counties (American Association of Nurse Anesthesiology [AANA], 2021). Physician specialists (surgeons, podiatrists, ophthalmologists, etc.) across the nation depend on CRNAs to meet the anesthesia needs of their communities (AANA, 2021). This is true for physicians in hospital, clinic, and outpatient settings. Although market demand for anesthesia providers is increasing, the number of providers added to the workforce annually is projected to decrease, which may lead to an anesthesia provider deficit crisis (Negrusa, Hogan, Cintina, et al., 2021; Peters & Young, 2022). This crisis may be exacerbated by the fact that many CRNAs either leave or consider leaving their positions on a yearly basis (Dexter et al., 2021). Retaining anesthesia providers is of paramount importance to maintaining patient access to care and this may be especially true for organizations in rural/underserved areas (Park et al., 2022). Moreover, considering the cost of replacing a single CRNA is approximately \$145,000 to \$157,000 (Mahoney et al., 2020), retention is critical to healthcare institutions that may incur a significant financial burden from high employee turnover (Peters & Young, 2022).

Turnover intention for CRNAs has been shown to be inversely related to job satisfaction (Mahoney et al., 2020). To enhance job satisfaction and the retention of CRNAs, it is imperative that new graduates transition successfully into the workforce (Tracy, 2017). To this point, experts indicate that a promising strategy for improving satisfaction and retention for advanced practice nurses is the implementation of formal postgraduate transition to practice (TTP) programs (orientation, fellowship, residency, etc.) where, after graduating, individuals are trained to develop the skills and confidence to practice on their own (Urbanowicz, 2019; Windey &

Cullen, 2018). Research supports this conclusion as advanced practice registered nurses (APRNs) who participate in TTP programs are more satisfied and less likely to consider leaving their positions (Park et al., 2022). Moreover, researchers find that APRNs who are a part of TTP programs are more likely to report successful role transition experiences and that these positive experiences are associated with significantly lower turnover intentions (Barnes et al., 2023).

Transition to Practice Programs

The Institutes of Medicine (IOM) recommends TTP programs for novice APRNs with the aim of facilitating retention, competency, and improved patient outcomes (IOM, 2011). In 2014, the Standards Revision Task Force (SRTF) developed by the Council on Accreditation of Nurse Anesthesia Educational Programs (COA, 2022) approved general standards for postgraduate CRNA fellowships to enhance the quality of teaching and learning among novice CRNAs (Gombkoto et al., 2014). Other accreditation standards exist for CRNAs and APRNs including guidelines from the Standards for Accreditation of Post-Graduate CRNA Fellowships (issued by the COA, 2018), the American Nurses Credentialing Center (2022), and the Consortium for Advanced Practice Providers Program Accreditation (CAPPPA, 2023). Nonetheless, literature concerning TTP programs reveals that organizations have varied ideas about what components are essential to successful first-year experiences for CRNAs and APRNs. Moreover, not all organizations with TTP programs provide these with the aim of accreditation and thus standards from accrediting agencies may not be universally applied in practice. Instead, research reveals that TTP programs are typically developed with respect to specific organizational needs and culture, and thus program components often vary across institutions (Cartwright, 2021; Goodwin et al., 2021; Robeano et al., 2019; Robinson, 2021).

Related to a lack of standardization, there is no consensus on what components are necessary or sufficient for successful TTP programs for CRNAs and APRNs. In fact, the efficacy of TTP programs themselves may be weak considering that evidence supporting their effectiveness is often derived from self-evaluation data (IOM, 2011), is limited to a few available studies, and often lacks “methodological rigor” (Speight et al., 2019, p. 562). Considering the varied nature of TTP programs and the lack of research regarding best practices, it is difficult to ascertain which components of TTP programs health care organizations should use. Specifically, the heterogeneous nature of different TTP programs and the lack of research regarding the efficacy of their components makes it difficult to link specific practices to outcomes typically associated with transition success including job satisfaction and retention.

Problem Statement

As novice CRNAs and APRNs transition into independent practitioners, they experience increased stress and psychological challenges that may decrease their job satisfaction and increase the likelihood that they leave their jobs within the first year (Barnes, 2015; Barnes et al., 2021, 2023). Organizations with high turnover rates suffer from the increased financial burden of training new staff and overworking existing staff which may impact their ability to meet the healthcare needs of the communities they serve (Barret & Wright, 2019). Transition to practice programs that provide support for novice APRNs and facilitate their acculturation into the workforce have been shown to successfully increase job satisfaction and decrease rates of turnover among advanced practice nurses (Park et al., 2022). However, despite the call to create structured TTP programs (IOM, 2011), newly graduated CRNAs identify a lack of these as a problem in their early practice experiences (Tracy, 2017). The same is true for APRNs in general as many receive no postgraduate training, and what exists is often informal (Barnes et al., 2023).

Although some organizations offer postgraduate TTP programs, these often vary by organization, structured guidelines for their successful implementation do not yet exist, and evidence of their impact on nursing outcomes could be stronger (Robinson, 2021; Speight et al., 2019).

Taken together, literature shows that formal postgraduate TTP programs may help facilitate successful role transition for newly graduated CRNAs and APRNs. However, there is a paucity of evidence with respect to best TTP strategies which makes it difficult for organizations to identify essential program components (Cartwright, 2021; Park et al., 2022; Tracy, 2017). Moreover, though it is argued that support during the transition from student to professional may lead to increased job satisfaction and lower rates of turnover for CRNAs and APRNs (Park et al., 2022; Tracy, 2017), individual studies that support these conclusions suffer from methodological limitations, and therefore these relationships have yet to be firmly established. Despite the presence of another systematic review on this topic (Speight et al., 2019), the current project extends this research to a larger population and includes different outcomes of interest such as retention and TTP program components. Considering the information presented, a systematic review examining TTP program components and their impact on job satisfaction and turnover may be valuable to stakeholders and new practitioners who stand to benefit from understanding how TTP programs and their individual components facilitate job satisfaction and promote retention in the first year of professional practice.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this DNP project was to conduct a systematic review of the literature to synthesize evidence related to the effectiveness of TTP programs for APRNs, including CRNAs and proposed recommendations regarding program components that are essential for successful

role transition by identifying practices that support successful TTP and examining their connection with job satisfaction and retention.

PRISMA

Medical practitioners often use the results of published research to guide their decision making. However, drawing appropriate conclusions from published work can be difficult because the number of research articles published every year makes the vast amount of information challenging to sort through (Leclercq et al., 2019). Considering this issue, systematic reviews are helpful because they condense a group of studies and provide summary information regarding general patterns in the data. Moreover, systematic reviews condense the state of knowledge on a particular topic and help researchers understand gaps in the literature (Page, McKenzie, et al., 2021). Well designed and executed systematic reviews can help advance a field of study by providing accurate evidence that healthcare professionals can use to guide their policy and practice (Page & Moher, 2017).

Systematic reviews are a crucial part of evidence-based practice, and they are often used to inform practice recommendations to improve patient care (Fleming et al., 2014; Kang, 2016). Due to their strengths, researchers claim that systematic reviews should be the “gold standard” for evidence-based decision making when health practitioners implement interventions for patients (South & Lorenc, 2020, p. 1). Because practitioners need the best information when making policy and practice decisions, it is important that systematic reviews are unbiased and reported in a detailed manner to help readers assess the strength of their conclusions (Fleming et al., 2014). Indeed, the value of a systematic review lies in what the authors did, what they found, and how well they communicate this information (Page & Moher, 2017).

The number of published systematic reviews and meta-analyses is growing exponentially (Kugler et al., 2023). Systematic reviews are broader than meta-analyses and include specific information such as a literature search strategy, inclusion and exclusion criteria for studies to be assessed, and tools used to evaluate study quality and validity (Borenstein et al., 2009). Meta-analyses include the effects from individual studies and calculate an average (weighted by sample size) to produce a synthesis of the overall data (Page, Moher, et al., 2021). Meta analyses can be conducted on their own, or as a part of a systematic review. Although systematic reviews and meta-analyses are being published more frequently, many have flaws that limit their credibility. For example, many systematic reviews are conducted poorly, or reported poorly, which limits readers' ability to trust the results (Sarkis-Onofre et al., 2021). Regarding the latter, an important part of assessing a study's quality stems from examining its methodology, and this can only be done if the methods are described in detail (Altman & Simera, 2016).

To help address shortcomings by authors when communicating their conclusions, an international group of researchers created guidelines in 1999 to help standardize the process for reporting meta-analyses. This set of standards was referred to as the Quality of Reporting of Meta Analysis (QUORUM) and was developed to improve transparency when reporting meta-analyses of randomized control trials (RCTs). In 2009, these guidelines were expanded to include systematic reviews and renamed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA; Page & Moher, 2017). The PRISMA guidelines include evidence-based recommendations to assist the community of research scientists with completeness and transparency when reporting the results of systematic reviews related to health interventions (Sarkis-Onofre et al., 2021), although it has been effectively applied to other types of scholarship including social and educational research (Page, McKenzie, et al., 2021).

Recently, the PRISMA 2020 guidelines were created to update the 2009 document with roughly 11 major changes. These changes include the addition of an abstract checklist, a recommendation that authors indicate their search process for all databases used, and a recommendation for declaring any conflicts of interest (Page, McKenzie, et al., 2021).

Largely, PRISMA guidelines ensure that authors provide an explanation for each step in the process of reporting systematic reviews so that readers can make informed decisions about the validity and strength of the findings (Fleming et al., 2014). Researchers who use PRISMA guidelines allow readers to evaluate the methodology used to come to conclusions, to determine the overlap between study characteristics and populations of interest, and to replicate (or build onto) existing systematic reviews (Page, McKenzie, et al., 2021). Further, researchers have found reports that explicitly mention PRISMA are more likely to be published in journals that have a higher impact factor, revealing a possible link between the use of PRISMA and both high-quality research and greater potential readership (Leclercq et al., 2019).

As of 2021, close to 60,000 reports have cited the recommendations endorsed by PRISMA (Page, McKenzie, et al., 2021). Additionally, 176 medical journals have endorsed PRISMA guidelines and require that authors apply these standards when submitting manuscripts for publication (Tam et al., 2017). Despite their apparent benefits and growing use, PRISMA guidelines have yet to be incorporated into the fabric of reporting in systematic reviews and meta-analyses. For instance, researchers examined 107 nursing journals and found that only approximately one third of these journals required or recommended that authors use the guidelines outlined in the PRISMA statement (Tam et al., 2017). Regarding systematic reviews, scholars found that the median adherence rate to the PRISMA guidelines in nursing journals was 64.9% (Tam et al., 2017). Similarly, many authors fail to follow PRISMA guidelines for meta-

analyses in a comprehensive manner (Leclercq et al., 2019). For example, in a sample of 206 meta-analyses, only four percent adhered to all 27 items in the PRISMA checklist and only 20% of the meta-analyses examined adhered to more than 90% of the PRISMA items (Leclercq et al., 2019). Another investigation into meta-analyses found that many of the items are reported sub-optimally with at least 11 items receiving little attention (Page & Moher, 2017). Journal editors, reviewers, and potential contributors are urged to continue to raise awareness about the PRISMA 2020 guidelines by referencing these in their instructions to authors for manuscript submission, looking for these when evaluating research, and using the guidelines when submitting their projects (Page, McKenzie, et al., 2021).

The PRISMA statement reflects a minimum set of recommendations for authors and encourages the transparent and complete reporting of systematic reviews (Sarkis-Onofre et al., 2021). In this regard, PRISMA guidelines for reporting systematic reviews provide authors with information about the clear dissemination of their work (Page & Moher, 2017). Moreover, experts argue that authors should review the PRISMA checklist early in the writing process to ensure they understand what information they may need to provide to readers (Page, McKenzie, et al., 2021). It is essential that researchers understand what items exist in the PRISMA checklist and how these items may benefit readers.

PRISMA Checklist

The PRISMA guidelines ensure that a common standard for best practice is met when reporting systematic reviews (Page, McKenzie, et al., 2021; South & Lorenc, 2020). By using PRISMA guidelines, readers of this paper can examine this project for potential bias and assess the validity and strength of the conclusions contained herein. For these reasons, the PRISMA 2020 guidelines were used as a framework for this systematic review.

Title (1)

Authors are asked to label a report as a systematic review or meta-analysis in the titles of their projects. Experts recommend that titles should explicitly use the term “systematic review” and if a meta-analysis is conducted, this should be made explicit as well (Page, Moher, et al., 2021). Some journals advocate that the topic of the study should also be noted in the title and that authors should consider using titles that include specific information such as: participants, interventions, comparators, outcomes, and study design (PICOS; Liberati et al., 2009). Doing so may help potential users (e.g., patients, policy makers, and providers) identify key aspects of the manuscript quickly (Page, Moher, et al., 2021). This information may also help catalogue the study correctly in various databases which may make it easier to locate (Page, Moher, et al., 2021; Shamseer et al., 2015). Thus, a researcher’s work is more likely to get noticed and scholars are less likely to duplicate projects which can contribute to research waste (Page, McKenzie, et al., 2021; Shamseer et al., 2015). In accordance with PRISMA guidelines, the title of this paper includes the words “systematic review” along with explicit information about the population of interest, intervention, and outcomes.

Abstract (2)

Authors who follow PRISMA guidelines for systematic reviews provide abstracts with specific information including background, methods, results, discussion, and other pertinent topics (e.g., funding and registration). This project includes the aforementioned information to help potential readers screen the manuscript swiftly and efficiently without having to visit the entire report (Liberati et al., 2009; Page, Moher, et al., 2021). If abstracts are complete, readers should be able to understand the content of a manuscript including the context of the study, the

objectives, and the results (Liberati et al., 2009). Terms present in keywords are also helpful for indexing research projects in bibliometric databases (Page, Moher, et al., 2021).

Rationale (3)

A rationale is critical for systematic reviews and meta-analyses because readers need to know why a review was conducted and what is already known about a particular subject (Liberati et al., 2009; Page, Moher, et al., 2021). Authors should also note the significance of the work and identify the primary audience (Shamseer et al., 2015). There are many ways to communicate a rationale including defining the importance of answering a specific question or addressing a limitation with respect to the current state of knowledge (Liberati et al., 2009). A rationale may include a description of what the authors wish to add to the current body of knowledge (Liberati et al., 2009). In this DNP project, a rationale is present in the introduction to explain why it is important to explore TTP programs for new APRNs and CRNAs.

Objectives (4)

Authors should provide an explicit and precise objective statement (Liberati et al., 2009; Page, Moher, et al., 2021). Doing so allows readers to comprehend the scope and applicability of the findings as these relate to their own needs (Liberati et al., 2009; Page, Moher, et al., 2021). Using a PICOS format for the objective statement provides information that readers might find particularly valuable (Shamseer et al., 2015). Objective statements also provide a rationale for various aspects of the report including search and eligibility criteria (Liberati et al., 2009). This DNP scholarly project contains an objective statement in the introduction section of the manuscript to alert readers to the explicit goals of this project.

Eligibility Criteria (5)

Appropriate eligibility criteria are critical features of systematic reviews (Shamseer et al., 2015). Eligibility criteria should be clearly stated to provide information pertaining to the types of studies, participants, interventions, and outcome measured (Liberati et al., 2009). Both study characteristics and report characteristics need to be reported (Liberati et al., 2009; Shamseer et al., 2015). The former includes data pertaining to PICOS, the latter includes language, study type (e.g., publication, dissertation, etc.), geographical location, and year of publication (Shamseer et al., 2015). Readers must understand the chosen eligibility criteria if they are going to successfully evaluate systematic reviews for comprehensiveness, validity, and bias (Liberati et al., 2009; Page, Moher, et al., 2021; Shamseer et al., 2015). This DNP project includes a detailed explanation of the eligibility criteria with specific attention to both study and report characteristics to enhance readers' ability to appraise the evidence presented.

Information Sources (6)

In accordance with PRISMA guidelines (Liberati et al., 2009), and to ensure transparency, it is noted that this scholarly project is authored by a student-faculty team consisting of one nurse anesthesia student and two doctoral-prepared nurse faculty including one from California State University, Fullerton and one from the Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia. In addition to reporting the individuals who authored this project, this report also includes information about what databases were used to conduct the searches and what date ranges were employed (Shamseer et al., 2015). Moreover, other search mechanisms (including checking reference lists) are articulated as well (Liberati et al., 2009). Authors add value to their reports by including sourcing information because doing so makes it easy for readers to understand the exact process that was carried out when evaluating the literature. This might be

particularly helpful if an update or extension is needed (Shamseer et al., 2015). Further, this information helps readers determine the completeness of a review (Page, Moher, et al., 2021).

Search Strategy (7)

A comprehensive search is important to ensure accuracy in systematic reviews (Shamseer et al., 2015). By providing information about the databases used, indexing terms, and limits applied to the search (Shamseer et al., 2015), authors can provide clarity about their search strategy and give readers confidence that all appropriate studies have been included (Liberati et al., 2009; Page, Moher, et al., 2021). This information might also help readers evaluate the appropriateness of the search and may help future researchers replicate or extend the search (Liberati et al., 2009). PRISMA 2020 recommends providing the full electronic search strategy for all databases, including how terms may have varied (Page, McKenzie, et al., 2021). For these reasons, and in accordance with PRISMA guidelines, this DNP scholarly project provides explicit information about the strategy utilized to search the literature in all databases used.

Selection Process (8)

Authors typically start with a wide swath of potential research reports and narrow these down for use in their systematic reviews (Liberati et al., 2009). Authors should be transparent about their selection process by reporting how they screened articles (e.g., using titles and/or abstracts) and if any articles were deemed inappropriate for review (Liberati et al., 2009; Page, Moher, et al., 2021). The goal of reporting the selection process is to promote objectivity and to avoid making mistakes when identifying potential research reports (Liberati et al., 2009; Page, Moher, et al., 2021; Shamseer et al., 2015). This DNP project provides information to readers about the process for selecting the articles used to draw conclusions including the conditions for screening and selecting articles.

Data Collection Process (9)

The data collection process is an important step when conducting systematic reviews because it helps readers understand how data was culled from research reports (Liberati et al., 2009). The goal of being forthcoming about the data collection process is to limit mistakes and to reduce bias to build readers' confidence in the results (Liberati et al., 2009; Page, Moher, et al., 2021). In addition, communicating the precise methods used to gather information is crucial for readers who are interested in replicating the process (Shamseer et al., 2015). This project contains information that informs readers of how data were collected/extracted from the primary sources and the steps taken to minimize errors in transcription.

Data Items (10)

It is important that authors tell readers about the information included in the data search including outcomes, variables, and other data collected (Liberati et al., 2009; Page, Moher, et al., 2021). This information is helpful for identifying whether bias could have been introduced as it pertains to reporting (Shamseer et al., 2015). Specifically, authors should be clear about what information they sought so that readers can ascertain the extent to which reported data aligns with the authors' prespecified outcomes (Shamseer et al., 2015). Authors should also be transparent about whether new variables were added after the review began so that readers are clear about the reasons these items were included (Page, Moher, et al., 2021). Additionally, authors should articulate their procedures for managing missing or incomplete data (Liberati et al., 2009). Independent decision making by the author regarding what outcomes are reported would introduce the possibility for bias, however this project utilized a tool to standardize the data collection process to help mitigate bias. Information about the data collection process is

provided to readers to appraise them of the outcomes and variables gathered from research reports. Information sought and collected is provided even if the results conflict.

Study Risk of Bias Assessment (11)

The summaries provided in systematic reviews and meta-analyses are only as valid as the studies they include (Liberati et al., 2009; Shamseer et al., 2015). As such, authors should provide information about what they did to evaluate the quality of the studies under consideration (Liberati et al., 2009), including their limitations (Page, Moher, et al., 2021). Adding this information helps readers determine the accuracy of the authors' bias assessment (Page, Moher, et al., 2021). Readers should know how study limitations were evaluated because quality standards might differ depending on the type of review conducted or tool applied (Page, Moher, et al., 2021). Some ideas that authors may consider when assessing quality include the sample, sample size, presence of a control, and the appropriate use of statistics (Liberati et al., 2009). This DNP scholarly project assessed research reports for bias using the *Quality Assessment Tool for Observational Cohort and Cross-Sectional Studies* from the National Institutes of Health (NIH; National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute, 2021).

Effect Measures (12)

Experts contend that authors should be transparent about the summary effect they use to evaluate results (Liberati et al., 2009). The effect that authors choose is important because it can impact how readers interpret results (Page, Moher, et al., 2021). This item may not be applicable to systematic reviews that do not include meta-analysis and therefore this DNP project does not report information pertaining to effect measures.

Synthesis Methods (13)

Decisions about which studies were included for data synthesis, how the data were prepared, and which model was chosen for analysis should be made clear to readers (Page, Moher, et al., 2021). This information is important because it helps readers understand the choices authors made when working with their data to reach conclusions. This criterion was not pertinent to this DNP project because data analysis and synthesis are typically reserved for meta-analyses (Tam et al., 2017).

Reporting Bias Assessment (14)

Reviewers may want to know if the data comprising a systematic review are biased (Liberati et al., 2009). To address this issue, authors may note if they completed an analysis of publication bias (usually reserved for meta-analyses), or if there are missing data from specific studies as the result of reporting bias. Reporting the methods used to assess bias will help readers determine if mistakes were made when doing so (Page, Moher, et al., 2021). Because this DNP scholarly project does not include a meta-analysis, a bias assessment is not reported. However, when data are missing from specific studies, this information is communicated to readers in this DNP scholarly project.

Certainty Assessment (15)

Certainty refers to the level of confidence authors have in the evidence they used to come to their conclusions (Page, Moher, et al., 2021). Authors should describe what factors they utilized to make assessments of certainty regarding the studies they examined. Some common issues to consider when assessing certainty include the consistency of findings, design limitations, and sample size (Page, Moher, et al., 2021). This information is essential for readers because it helps them understand the authors' justification for their conclusions. Because

PRISMA guidelines advocate for a certainty assessment, this DNP project provides certainty information about the evidence utilized.

Study Selection (16)

In accordance with PRISMA guidelines, this project includes a flow diagram as a visual aid to summarize the process of study selection (Liberati et al., 2009). Using a flow diagram facilitates the reporting of the process used for selecting articles, including those that were searched for, and ultimately retained for use. The diagram includes information about database searches, hand searches, and reference searches (Liberati et al., 2009). Guidelines from PRISMA recommend that each search includes the total number of records located, the number of records excluded from titles and abstracts, the number of records evaluated, and primary reasons for excluding reports (Liberati et al., 2009; Page, Moher, et al., 2021). It is important for readers to understand where most of the studies originated from and how many research reports were excluded (and the reasoning) at each stage of the process (Liberati et al., 2009). This information may help readers identify bias that might have occurred, for example, from primarily sourcing references or experts (e.g., citation or publication bias; Liberati et al., 2009). Additionally, study selection information is essential for researchers who want to duplicate or update the systematic review (Page, Moher, et al., 2021).

Study Characteristics (17)

For readers to best evaluate a summary study, they must be able to evaluate the studies it uses (Liberati et al., 2009). Thus, sufficient information about the included studies should be present for readers to draw their own conclusions (Liberati et al., 2009; Page, Moher, et al., 2021). Authors should communicate the specific components of each study including the methods, intervention, and both primary and secondary outcomes (Liberati et al., 2009). After

studies are summarized, authors should provide an overview of conclusions in the form of a narrative summary of the combined results (Liberati et al., 2009). These results are often best presented in the form of a table (Page, Moher, et al., 2021). Consistent with PRISMA guidelines, this DNP project includes information in the form of a table to present pertinent information about the individual studies which are used to draw conclusions. Tabular information allows readers to appraise the included studies as these contribute to general conclusions.

Risk of Bias in Studies (18)

Readers should be able to assess the risk of bias in specific studies to evaluate the systematic review's internal validity (Liberati et al., 2009; Page, Moher, et al., 2021). To make this possible, this DNP project reports the methodology of each study included in the synthesis (Liberati et al., 2009), and presents information pertaining to the risk of bias for each outcome assessed (Page, Moher, et al., 2021). Specificity is important because if authors only report general information, it will be difficult for readers to assess a study's characteristics or to draw conclusions about how results were interpreted (Page, Moher et al., 2021).

Results of Individual Studies (19)

Information related to outcomes examined from individual studies should be communicated to readers to provide information about the contribution of each (Liberati et al., 2009; Page, Moher, et al., 2021). This information is helpful for researchers who want to produce an update of a systematic review or for individuals who wish to perform their own data analyses (Page, Moher, et al., 2021). In meta-analyses, this information is typically provided in a forest plot that allows readers to view basic summary data for individual studies. This DNP project does not include a forest plot, but information related to outcomes from individual studies are reported in a summative table.

Results of Syntheses (20)

In accordance with PRISMA recommendations, the results of the syntheses made in this scholarly project are clearly stated, including narrative descriptions of the outcomes and potential bias (Liberati et al., 2009; Page, Moher et al., 2021). This DNP project also communicates how study populations and research designs impact the outcomes (Liberati et al., 2009). This synthesized data may help readers draw specific conclusions about how bias could have affected the results or determine if any patterns or differences are due to specific study characteristics.

In addition, analyses with respect to heterogeneity are typically presented in the results section to help readers understand the variability in summary effects (Page, Moher, et al., 2021). Issues of heterogeneity indicate the existence of possible moderators which indicate that differences in outcomes exist depending on some other factor (Page, Moher, et al., 2021). This factor may include the population under consideration, different interventions (e.g., different dosing), or some other unknown cause. Typically, statistics related to heterogeneity are derived from meta-analyses and for this reason they are not presented in this DNP project. However, differences with respect to potential moderators are discussed.

Reporting Biases (21)

Reporting biases helps authors communicate the risk of bias from missing results and allows readers to ascertain the trustworthiness of the systematic review (Page, Moher, et al., 2021). This assessment may help readers understand how robust the conclusions are with respect to potentially missing data (e.g., selective reporting bias; Liberati et al., 2009). Primarily, two types of biases should be considered when reporting a systematic review, these include publication bias and reporting bias. Publication bias refers to the potential impact of unpublished studies and is typically reserved for meta-analyses. Reporting bias includes instances where

individual studies fail to provide information that was measured, but that did not support researchers' conclusions (e.g., nonsignificant results). In this project, information about individual studies that fail to report key results is included.

Certainty of Evidence (22)

According to PRISMA, authors should report their level of confidence for each of the outcomes assessed (Page, Moher, et al., 2021). Authors should also clearly communicate their reasoning for their conclusions. Furthermore, PRISMA guidelines recommend that authors use a table to help communicate these findings (Page, Moher, et al., 2021). Additionally, PRISMA guidelines recommend that authors communicate certainty assessments wherever conclusions are provided (Page, Moher, et al., 2021). This DNP project includes information about the quality of data used to draw conclusions to help readers understand the level of certainty associated with assessments made regarding the outcomes.

Discussion (23)

Authors should provide a balanced summary of their findings in the discussion section, including clinical relevance (Liberati et al., 2009). Moreover, the findings should be communicated to specific interested parties or audiences (e.g., patients, health-care providers, and policy makers) and placed into a larger context by making note of the results as they relate to other, similar projects (Page, Moher, et al., 2021). Shortcomings should also be discussed to help readers understand the limitations and generalizability of the conclusions (Liberati et al., 2009; Page, Moher, et al., 2021). Importantly, authors should be forthcoming when conclusions cannot be drawn due to a lack of data (Liberati et al., 2009). Authors should also articulate ideas pertaining to future directions for research to help readers understand potential next steps regarding the phenomena of interest (Liberati et al., 2009; Page, Moher, et al., 2021). At the end

of this scholarly project, a discussion section is included to summarize the findings, note important limitations, and place the conclusions into the larger context of successful TTP programs.

Registration and Protocol (24)

When authors use a protocol, they create transparency in their work by demonstrating that their actions in conducting the systematic review matched their intentions; taken together this reduces bias (Shamseer et al., 2015; Page, Moher, et al., 2021). Protocols help researchers avoid making decisions about methodology or objectives after the fact – such as selective outcome reporting (Liberati et al., 2009). Selective outcome reporting is a well-established reporting phenomenon affecting many published Cochrane Reviews (Liberati et al., 2009). Moreover, using a protocol helps prevent the duplication of records because researchers can access protocols before they begin a project to examine what is currently being studied or what has previously been studied (Page, Moher, et al., 2021; Shamseer et al., 2015). Registering a systematic review with a protocol registry such as the international Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews (PROSPERO), can also be a useful strategy for reducing publication bias (Liberati et al., 2009). This DNP scholarly project proposal has been submitted to PROSPERO and is awaiting registration (registration number: CRD42023415792, Appendix A).

Support (25)

Authors of systematic reviews should disclose if they received funding to conduct their research (Liberati et al., 2009; Page, Moher, et al., 2021). The role of funders should be made transparent with regard to the creation, assessment, or dissemination of a project because it helps readers determine if there is a potential for influence (Shamseer et al., 2015). This is important because sponsorship bias is known to exist. For example, experts have found that systematic

reviews and meta-analyses supported by a sponsor (e.g., pharmaceutical products) report more favorable results (Liberati et al., 2009; Shamseer et al., 2015). Systematic reviews have the potential to change practice and policy, therefore authors should provide full transparency regarding support (Liberati et al., 2009; Page, Moher, et al., 2021). The authors of this study did not receive any funding and do not have any conflicts of interest to report.

Competing Interests (26)

According to PRISMA, authors are encouraged to be transparent about any relationships that might threaten the integrity and credibility of their results (Page, Moher, et al., 2021).

Authors are expected to communicate the existence of relationships that may be relevant to, or may have impacted, the review. If these relationships exist, authors should report how these were managed (Page, Moher, et al., 2021). Readers of this DNP project should be aware that there are no relevant relationships to report that might impact the integrity and credibility of the conclusions.

Availability of Data, Code, and Other Materials (27)

According to PRISMA, authors may want to share their original data files from their projects (Page, Moher, et al., 2021). There are several reasons for this including allowing other researchers to identify possible errors, to replicate the study's findings, and/or to build on the body of knowledge (Page, Moher, et al., 2021). This information may be most applicable to researchers who have data sets associated with their work or codes for statistical analyses that may be beneficial to readers. This criterion does not apply to this project as there are no data to which readers would need access.

Review of Literature

The literature review for this DNP project yielded few studies exploring the relationship between postgraduate TTP programs for CRNAs and job satisfaction and retention. Considering this, APRNs were included to investigate TTP experiences and their association with the outcomes of interest. Crucially, although studies examining the link between TTP and job satisfaction and retention exist for APRNs, individual studies have limitations which prohibit definitive conclusions, and the literature review did not reveal any studies that have been conducted as systematic reviews to summarize this literature with respect to the outcome variables pertinent to the CRNA community. Thus, a systematic review may help researchers and practitioners build confidence with respect to the associations between TTP programs, job satisfaction, and retention for APRNs. As such, the purpose of this DNP project was to conduct a systematic review of the literature to synthesize evidence related to the effectiveness of TTP programs for APRNs, including CRNAs. This DNP scholarly project also made recommendations regarding program components that are essential for successful role transition by identifying practices that support successful TTP and examining their connection with job satisfaction and retention.

The population of interest is CRNAs which are a type of APRN with critical care training and a degree in anesthesia practice – usually a master’s or doctoral degree (Vitale & Lyons, 2021). Due to a lack of evidence examining only CRNAs in TTP programs, studies involving all APRNs were included in this systematic review. Advanced practice registered nurses comprise a more general population of interest that includes CRNAs and nurses with similar levels of training and practice responsibilities. More specifically, the term APRN refers to any of the four roles deemed to be at an advanced practice level (Goudreau, 2022). These roles include CRNAs,

Certified Nurse Practitioners (CNPs, NPs), Certified Registered Nurse Midwives (CNMs), and Clinical Nurse Specialists (CNS; Goudreau, 2022). Advanced Practice Registered Nurses complete specific, advanced practice training and, in contrast to registered nurses (RNs), practice and prescribe independently (although this may vary by state and institution; Goudreau, 2022).

Transition to Practice Strategies

As newly graduated CRNAs and other APRNs adapt to increased levels of autonomy and responsibility, they face numerous challenges and experience increased stress (Flinter & Hart 2017; Pleshkan & Hussey, 2020; Tracy, 2017). Considering this, the IOM (2011) recommends postgraduate training programs for novice APRNs to support their transition into practice with the goals of improving retention, expanding competency, and improving outcomes for patients. In the literature, strategies to support successful role transition include new employee orientation, onboarding, and fellowship or residency programs (Urbanowicz, 2019).

Orientation is the process of becoming familiar with hospital policies, procedures, and mission statements of organizations (Garcia et al., 2017), whereas onboarding is a more organized process of longer duration (typically 30-90 days). Onboarding activities are aimed at assimilating new employees into the culture of a healthcare system (Garcia et al., 2017). During the onboarding process, new employees may be paired with preceptors to assist with completing paperwork (e.g., orientation checklist, needs assessments, etc.), or with mentors who serve as role models for behaviors that lead to successful integration into the organization (Garcia et al., 2017). Regarding the latter, mentors encourage the development of leadership skills and personal growth which contribute to stronger organizational commitment and retention (Garcia et al., 2017).

Fellowships and residencies are formal and structured in design. Accredited fellowship programs follow specific program guidelines and award sub-specialty certifications (e.g., pediatric or advanced pain management for CRNAs post initial certification), typically through affiliation with a university (COA, 2018). Residency programs offer similar support in terms of mentorship, education, and patient care experiences, but generally do not grant sub-specialty certification (although these do often include training in specialty areas). Accredited fellowship or residency programs typically consist of comprehensive, lengthy (usually six months to one year), and individualized didactic educational and clinical training (Sutor & Painter, 2020). These programs frequently include recurring meetings with mentors/faculty, competency and self-evaluations, and performance milestones (Sutor & Painter, 2020). Considering this, some organizations offer official, accredited fellowship or residency programs for new graduate APRNs (COA, 2018). However, other organizations label their postgraduate experiences for novice APRNs as residencies or fellowships, despite a lack of accreditation (e.g., Cartwright, 2021; Painter et al., 2019; Zapatka et al., 2014).

Transition to practice programs are relatively new for APRNs and the terms used to differentiate these experiences have not been well-defined (Firth & Marsan, 2016). Indeed, the terms *fellowship* and *residency* (along with other terms such as *orientation*, *education*, *onboarding*, and *training programs*) are often used to describe similar TTP programs in the literature. In accordance with previous research on the subject (e.g., Barnes et al., 2023), experiences that are labeled as residency, fellowship, onboarding, or orientation programs were referred to as TTP programs for the purposes of this DNP project (irrespective of program type) as long as these provide structured and sustained assistance to new APRNs during their role transition.

Transition to Practice Program Components

Organizations vary regarding the structural components that comprise their TTP programs. However, in the last 15 years, accrediting bodies have begun to outline standards to provide recommendations for best practice. For example, in their Standards for Accreditation of Post-Graduate CRNA Fellowships guidelines, the COA (2018) provides a framework for the components deemed necessary for CRNA TTP programs. Specifically, the COA (2018) requires that accredited fellowship programs employ specialized training with credentialed experts, use mentors to provide individualized guidance, and deliver regular performance evaluations. According to the COA (2018), the curriculum for post graduate CRNA fellowships must also include didactic and patient care experiences to ensure practitioner competency while meeting identified goals and objectives. Furthermore, the COA (2018) maintains that faculty and administrators should be open to organizational program improvements based on feedback from fellowship participants. The recommendations from the COA are general and details regarding program length, course content, desired outcomes, and specific learning experiences have been left to the discretion of the implementing organization. Fellowships that meet the criteria reported above are few. According to the most recent update, there are only six accredited programs available to new CRNAs (COA, 2022). Not all TTP programs for CRNAs are accredited, other types of programs exist and these may or may not adhere to the standards put forth by the COA. Therefore, organizations may have programs that include onboarding, orientation, or similar experiences to support CRNA TTP without including all the elements required by an accrediting agency. For example, Robinson (2021), created a formal orientation program for a single organization which included mentorship experiences, offsite anesthesia training, and provision of support for difficult decision-making.

Similar to CRNA populations, guidelines for postgraduate experiences also exist for APRNs and RNs. As an example, IOM (2011) recommends TTP programs (in general) as viable tools for achieving APRN and RN competency, retention, and improved patient care. The National Nurse Practitioner Residency and Fellowship Training Consortium provides more specific guidance in their detailed accreditation standards that include competency in particular workplace domains (e.g., providing appropriate referrals, utilizing telehealth, and participating in quality improvement (QI) projects). These standards are explicitly stated in the CAPPPA (2023) guidelines and the criteria necessary to meet each competency domain include detailed sub-competency requirements for new practitioners. Similar to some CRNA TTP programs, several organizations that provide APRN TTP programs have not yet gained accreditation. A recent systematic review of APRN TTP programs found that these programs included several shared components such as mentorship, professional socialization activities, interprofessional training (e.g., communication with other disciplines), and direct patient care experiences (Speight et al., 2019). Despite their similarities, TTP programs are often developed based on specific organizational need and culture. For instance, Robeano et al. (2019) created an organization-specific TTP program focused on stress reduction, decreased workload, and peer mentorship. Cartwright (2021) reported a fellowship program that included a didactic experience, mentorship, and a QI project. Goodwin et al. (2021) designed their own TTP program including didactic courses, clinical experiences, simulations, case-based learning, and mentorship.

As should be evident, organizations have varied ideas about what components are essential to successful TTP programs and these differences are reflected in the experiences they provide to their advanced practice nurses. Although accreditation guidelines exist for CRNAs and APRNs, not all organizations offering TTP programs provide these with the aim of

accreditation. Thus, these standards may not be universally applied. Therefore, it might be appropriate to conclude that there is no consensus regarding what components are necessary or sufficient for successful TTP programs. Moreover, although preferences for TTP experiences have been reported (Tracy, 2017), sparse evidence links specific transition components to outcomes of importance (e.g., satisfaction, retention) as reported by organizations and outlined by the IOM (2011).

Job Satisfaction

Researchers who study job satisfaction among CRNAs indicate that the term reflects a person's level of contentment as it pertains to their ability to achieve the goals of their job (Mahoney et al., 2020). Increased job satisfaction has been linked to retention and decreased turnover intentions for APRNs (Fasbender et al., 2019; Pasaron, 2013) and CRNAs (Mahoney et al., 2020). Moreover, higher levels of job satisfaction among APRNs have been linked to improved patient care (Pasaron, 2013).

Job satisfaction is influenced by many intrinsic and extrinsic factors. Intrinsic factors such as intrinsic motivators of job performance are linked to job satisfaction and include personal achievement, growth potential, peer recognition, a sense of responsibility, and the contentment individuals experience when performing their work (Misener & Cox, 2001). Extrinsic factors that affect job satisfaction include the work environment and conditions, compensation, interpersonal relationships, job status, administration, and supervision (Misener & Cox, 2001). Scholars agree that supporting intrinsic motivators of job satisfaction are more effective than extrinsic motivators such as bonuses or salary rewards (Niskala et al., 2020; Sabanciogullari & Dogan, 2015).

The most frequently used tool for measuring job satisfaction among APRNs and CRNAs is the *Misener Nurse Practitioner Job Satisfaction Scale* (MNPJSS; Misener & Cox, 2001). The MNPJSS is a 44-item survey using a six item Likert scale with scores ranging from (1) *very dissatisfied* to (6) *very satisfied*. Scores are added together and range from 44-264. Based on this scale, job satisfaction is operationalized as a function of six factors including: (a) intra-practice partnership/collegiality (e.g., administrative support, respect, policy input), (b) challenge/autonomy (e.g., scope of practice, case complexity, direct patient care), (c) professional, social, and community interaction (e.g., peer recognition, interdisciplinary interactions, quality of support persons), (d) professional growth (e.g., opportunity to serve on committees, continuing education, research involvement), (e) time (e.g., ample time to adequately perform a physical assessment or chart review), and (f) benefits (e.g., retirement plan, vacation time; Misener & Cox, 2001). The MNPJSS is a reliable tool which has demonstrated an overall Cronbach's alpha score of .96, indicating excellent internal consistency (Misener & Cox, 2001). Each of the six subscales also indicate acceptable reliability ranging from .79 to .94 (Misener & Cox, 2001).

Retention

Retention refers to employees who stay employed for a period of time (typically between one to three years; Urbanowicz, 2019) and is measured in longitudinal studies by assessing employment status in an organization at a predetermined date. Relatedly, turnover intention reflects an individual's intent to leave an organization. Studies often measure an employee's intent to leave/turnover intention in cross-sectional studies because it is a strong predictor of their future behavior (Fasbender et al., 2019). Turnover intention can be measured by using a validated tool to ascertain the likelihood that an individual may leave an organization. For

example, the *Anticipated Turnover Scale* (ATS; Hinshaw & Atwood, 1985) has been used to determine the likelihood that a nurse will leave their current position voluntarily (Barlow & Zangaro, 2010).

Retention and turnover intentions are of great concern to healthcare leadership because of the financial costs associated with the recruitment and training of new employees (Hagan & Curtis, 2018). Indeed, scholars estimate the cost of replacing one CRNA is approximately \$150,000 – fees that may be passed on to private citizens in the form of higher consumer prices (Mahoney et al., 2020). In addition, when employees leave their positions, an increased burden is placed on the existing workforce who struggle to absorb the added workload from staffing deficits (Barret & Wright, 2019; Fasbender et al., 2019). Moreover, nurses who work in environments that are short-staffed may be prone to making errors, providing lower quality care, and decreased job satisfaction (Fasbender et al., 2019).

Relationship Between Transition to Practice and Job Satisfaction

Researchers have found that newly graduated nurses face difficulties after graduation and note that post graduate TTP programs may help nurses successfully transition from graduate school to professional practice (MacKay et al., 2017). In one study, more than half of recent APRN graduates noted that they felt unprepared and found the first year of practice to be difficult, with problems ranging from independent decision making to complex case management (MacKay et al., 2017). Similarly, Barnes et al. (2021) argued that role transitions for nurse practitioners “can be described as stressful and turbulent, leading to decreased job satisfaction and increased intent to leave” (p. 79). In the case of CRNAs, literature shows that new graduates are often frustrated with a lack of TTP support (Tracy, 2017). These CRNAs noted that a deficiency in post-graduate training programs resulted in increased frustration, stress, and

anxiety. Conversely, APRNs who are involved with TTP programs report more satisfaction with their roles (Barnes, 2015).

In the general nursing literature, researchers have found that TTP programs help facilitate job satisfaction for new graduates (Missen et al., 2014). Specifically, in a systematic review, Missen et al. (2014) found that supportive programs aimed at helping new graduates transition to professional practice resulted in increased levels of job satisfaction. Proponents of TTP programs argue that the same is true for APRNs (Barnes, 2015). With regard to CRNAs, Tracy (2017) contends that “employers may find that implementing a mentorship program for recently graduated CRNAs by experienced CRNAs is a way to promote CRNA role transition and increase CRNA retention and satisfaction” (p. 443). However, quantitative research linking TTP and job satisfaction is scant with respect to CRNAs. Although researchers have studied CRNAs with respect to job satisfaction (Mahoney et al., 2020; Negrusa, Hogan, Jordan, et al., 2021) as well as TTP (Tracy, 2017), few provide a link between these constructs.

Literature examining APRNs with respect to TTP and job satisfaction is better established, though much of what is reported is difficult to interpret. For example, some research reports note that TTP programs lead to increased satisfaction for APRNs but fail to provide appropriate statistics for these results. Specifically, some studies fail to provide significance tests comparing TTP versus control groups or pre-tests (Horner, 2017; Moss, 2021), while others fail to report statistical information at all (Painter et al., 2019). In addition, many of these studies include small samples (Cartwright, 2021; Moss, 2021; Painter et al., 2019).

Due to the lack of quantitative research linking TTP programs to job satisfaction for CRNAs, practitioners may find it challenging to draw conclusions from the literature. Moreover, individual studies that do exist for APRNs do not include strong evidence to guide decisions.

Considering this, a systematic review examining the general trends in these data may be helpful for establishing a link between TTP programs to job satisfaction in the body of research that does exist.

Relationship Between Transition to Practice and Retention

Advanced practice registered nurses experience a variety of emotions associated with their first year of practice including stress, anxiety, frustration, inadequacy, and uncertainty that may lead to decreased confidence, job satisfaction, and turnover (Barnes, 2015; Tracy, 2017). Turnover is expensive for organizations because when employees leave, organizations are forced to recruit and train new workers, as well as pay current personnel overtime (Mahoney et al., 2020). Moreover, CRNA turnover can lead to a variety of problems for health care organizations including a lack of professionals to provide patient care and overworking existing staff which may lead to exhaustion (Barret & Wright, 2019; Mahoney et al., 2020). These problems may be more salient than organizations expect considering that, in a national sample of CRNAs, 53% either left their jobs or considered leaving their jobs in a given year (Dexter et al., 2021).

Considering the issues APRNs face when starting their careers, programs designed to help novice APRNs TTP may be critical to promoting retention (Barnes, 2015; McGrath et al., 2021; Tracy, 2017). However, to demonstrate the efficacy of TTP programs, the IOM (2011) states that researchers should evaluate role transition support programs to confirm their ability to reduce nurse turnover. So far, researchers have not addressed this issue thoroughly, if at all, in the CRNA population. However, research does exist with APRNs and RNs, and results from these studies indicate that there is an association between TTP programs and reduced turnover. For example, pertaining to APRNs, researchers have found that, compared to individuals who did not have a formal orientation, those who received orientation scored higher on the *Novice*

Nurse Practitioner Role Transition (NNPRT) Scale (Barnes et al., 2023). Importantly, scores on the NNPRT were found to be negatively associated with turnover intentions. Similar results were found in a sample of NPs with residency training who had a higher likelihood of reporting that they never considered leaving their position compared to individuals who did not receive residency training (Park et al., 2022).

Studies linking TTP programs and RN turnover/retention are more numerous, and several systematic reviews have provided evidence of an association between TTP and reduced turnover. For example, researchers examined data from 1,032 nurses at 70 hospitals and found that nurses who had TTP training had a higher one-year retention rate (84.5%) compared to nurses who did not (73.7%; Silvestre et al., 2017). In a more comprehensive project, Asper (2019) conducted a review of the literature and found that nurse TTP programs increased retention rates for new nurses after one year. According to Asper, the majority of studies reported less than a 10% turnover rate, which was lower than the national average. Similarly, Missen et al. (2014) conducted a systematic review of the literature and reported that all studies reviewed showed improvement in retention rates for nurses who engaged in TTP programs.

Although there is much data on the association between TTP programs and retention for RNs, scant data was retrieved for CRNAs. Moreover, that which exists for APRNs is often reported without appropriate statistical information (Scholtz et al., 2014; Taylor et al., 2017) or with small sample sizes (Cartwright, 2021; Painter et al., 2019). Considering this, a systematic review of the data associated with APRN TTP and its association with retention/turnover may be helpful for building researchers' confidence in the connection between these variables.

Systematic Review

Transition to practice programs are not without their drawbacks and thus, implementing these programs without evidence of their benefit is not advisable (Speight et al., 2019). One drawback of implementing TTP programs is the potential that such programs may create the perception that APRNs are not ready for practice upon graduation (American Nurses Association [ANA], 2014; Speight et al., 2019). For this reason, the ANA (2014) maintains that new nurse graduates may benefit from post-graduate programs when transitioning between practice settings, but additional training is not needed. A second drawback of TTP programs includes their cost. Costs of postgraduate TTP programs include those associated with training, and lost productivity for mentors who share their time teaching (Bush & Lowery, 2016; Goodwin et al., 2021). Other costs include time for training new hires that may come at the expense of patient access to care (Speight et al., 2019). Because there is limited public funding available to help APRNs transition into practice after graduation (Goodwin et al., 2021), organizations themselves are financially responsible for these programs. As such, the investment into TTP programs is only justified to organizations if a benefit can be demonstrated (Silvestre et al., 2017). As Speight et al. (2019) argued, a debate still exists regarding whether postgraduate TTP programs are necessary or if these compromise patient access while adding unnecessary cost and potentially communicating a lack of new graduate preparedness.

Although several studies examining the link between TTP and both job satisfaction/and retention for APRNs exist, data from these studies have not been evaluated comprehensively to produce reliable recommendations. Moreover, much of this data comes from studies with methodological constraints (e.g., a lack of appropriate statistical information or small sample sizes) that limit the confidence researchers might have in their conclusions. By conducting this

systematic review, trends in the existing literature were identified to provide both researchers and practitioners with a summary of data that could build confidence regarding the associations between TTP programs, job satisfaction, and retention for APRNs in general and CRNAs in specific.

Methods

Search Strategy

A literature search was conducted to identify journal articles that focused on postgraduate TTP programs for novice CRNAs and APRNs. In accordance with PRISMA recommendations, assessment of records was conducted by two reviewers. The search was conducted in PubMed, OVID, CINAHL, and Cochrane databases through the California State University, Fullerton (CSUF) library system, as well as the AANA journal archive, without time delimitation. In addition, Google Scholar was used to search for relevant articles. However, an initial search produced results in the tens of thousands. Therefore, a time delimitation of five years (2018-2023) was applied in this search to ensure more recent results were retrieved. The following search terms were used in various combinations; *Certified registered nurse anesthetist, CRNA, orientation, onboarding, role transition, training program, fellowship, preceptorship, satisfaction, retention, turnover, and attrition*. Due to the lack of studies retrieved involving CRNAs, a subsequent search was conducted in the same manner using the terms *Advanced Practice Registered Nurse* and *APRN* to broaden the number of results retrieved.

Articles that met inclusion criteria contained information pertaining to TTP, were peer-reviewed, available in the English language, available in full text, examined postgraduate training for novice CRNAs or APRNs (who graduated less than five years prior to measurement or included studies that asked participants to recall their experiences with TTP programs), and

examined outcomes related to job satisfaction and/or job retention. Reference lists from published articles were searched to identify additional articles. One author was contacted directly for a copy of their publication. Titles and abstracts were screened for eligibility independently by two reviewers (B.D., S.A.), disagreement was resolved by a third reviewer (S.G.).

A total of 744 articles were retrieved from databases, an additional 1,620 publications were identified through other search methods (e.g., Google Scholar, reference searching, academic journals). After duplicates ($n = 117$) and exclusions ($n = 2,195$) were removed, 52 articles were identified for closer review. Forty three articles were excluded for reasons including: written in foreign language ($n = 1$), literature review ($n = 8$), lack of statistical data to draw conclusions ($n = 3$), unrelated intervention ($n = 3$), capstone projects, master's theses, or dissertation ($n = 4$), unrelated outcomes ($n = 20$), or not representative of the population of interest (e.g., did not include novice practitioners or focused on pre- as opposed to post-licensure participants; $n = 4$). The remaining nine studies were included in this review; five were located through databases and four were found through the other search methods noted above (Figure 1, Appendix B).

Data Extraction and Synthesis

Data was extracted in accordance with PRISMA guidelines to provide transparency (Page, Moher, et al., 2021). Publication details including author(s), publication year, objectives, methodology and results (e.g., participants, setting, study design, data collection, measurement tools, outcome statistics) were manually extracted from each study and presented in tabular format (Table 1, Appendix C). In accordance with PRISMA guidelines, no new variables were added to the investigation while data were extracted.

Results

Overview/Study Characteristics

All studies included in this systematic review were conducted in the U.S. Five studies used a cohort study design to investigate the impact of fellowship or TTP programs on outcomes of interest (Cartwright, 2021; Erickson et al., 2021; Jackson et al., 2023; Scholtz et al., 2014; Taylor et al., 2017). The remaining four studies utilized cross-sectional survey designs to investigate associations between TTP programs and outcomes of interest (Barnes et al., 2023; Bryant & Parker, 2019; Bush & Lowery, 2016; Park et al., 2022). Several types of healthcare organizations were represented in the studies including universities, a children's hospital, "for profit" and "not-for-profit" hospitals, and outpatient clinics. Of the studies that reported demographic data, more than 89% of study participants were female and more than 75% were Caucasian (Barnes et al., 2023; Bryant & Parker, 2019; Bush & Lowery, 2016; Park et al., 2022). Of the five studies that examined job satisfaction, three studies used the MNPJSS (Bryant & Parker, 2019; Bush & Lowery, Cartwright, 2021), one created a tool (the Novice Nurse Practitioner Role Transition [NNPRT] scale) to measure successful role transition which includes job satisfaction (Barnes et al., 2023), and one used an author-created categorical scale (Park et al., 2022). Of the seven studies that reported information related to retention, five evaluated internal turnover data (Cartwright, 2021; Erickson et al., 2021; Jackson et al., 2023; Scholtz et al., 2014; Taylor et al., 2017), one used the AT Scale (Barnes et al., 2021), and one used single item "yes/no" question regarding intent to leave (Park et al., 2022).

Critical Appraisal

Each article's level of evidence was determined using the Johns Hopkins levels of evidence pyramid (Dang et al., 2022). Healthcare advocates rely upon the Johns Hopkins

standards to make informed decisions about clinical practice and research design. Specifically, the hierarchical framework is used to critically appraise research evidence and communicate the confidence scholars have in the research findings. Five studies were determined to be Level V, and four were Level III.

Quality Assessment

The NIH Quality Assessment Tool for Observational Cohort and Cross-Sectional Studies (National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute, 2021) was used to assess the quality of studies (Table 2, Appendix D). Scores were tallied based on the presence/absence of specific criteria using a series of 14 items with the aim of categorizing studies along three dimensions including “poor” (0-4 items), “fair” (5-10 items), and “good” (11-14 items; Bagias et al., 2021). The scores for studies used in this systematic review ranged from four to eight. Taken together, the nine studies averaged a score of 5.55 out of a possible 14 points. This score represents a “fair” rating according to the NIH quality assessment tool (Bagias et al., 2021). None of the included studies received a rating of “good”. The studies scored highest on questions four (“Were all the subjects selected or recruited from the same or similar populations?”), seven (“Was the time frame between exposure and outcomes sufficient?”), and nine (“Were the exposure measures clearly defined, valid, reliable, consistent?”). The studies scored lowest on questions that were not applicable to their study designs including question eight representing differing levels of exposures and question ten which measured exposures more than once over time.

Transition to Practice Outcomes

Job Satisfaction

Results from each of the five studies examined indicated that TTP programs were associated with increased job satisfaction. This was true regardless of the way job satisfaction

was measured (MNPJSS, Bryant & Parker, 2019; Bush & Lowery, 2016; Cartwright, 2021; NNPRT, Barnes et al., 2023; author-created measurement tool, Park et al., 2022). Bryant and Parker (2019) used individual items from the MNPJSS to study job satisfaction. Although individuals who participated in a fellowship program reported higher satisfaction for some of the items, the majority of these were nonsignificant. Only one study examined APRN experiences from a cohort that had been actively enrolled in a specific TTP program (Cartwright, 2021). The other studies asked participants to reflect on their TTP experiences without regard for the type of experience or the time interval since completion. Two studies controlled for covariates to study the unique effect of TTP programs on job satisfaction. Park et al. (2022) controlled for age, sex, race, employment setting, and earnings. Bush and Lowery (2016) conducted a multiple linear regression controlling for years of NP experience and state regulatory environment. Bush and Lowery (2016) provided data about the coefficient of determination indicating a small impact of TTP experiences on job satisfaction ($R^2 = .04$).

Retention

Seven studies examined retention which was measured through intent to leave and turnover data. Together, results indicated that TTP programs are associated with higher retention. Specifically, results from two studies indicate that TTP programs were associated with lower intent to leave. One study measured intent to leave with the ATS (Barnes et al., 2023). Scores on the ATS were negatively correlated with the NNPRT ($r = -.59, p < .001$) which is associated with participation in a formal orientation program (Barnes et al., 2023). In another study, intent to leave was measured with a single item (yes/no) referring to the question: “Have you ever considered leaving the primary nursing position?” (Park et al., 2022). Results from five studies indicated that TTP programs were associated with lower turnover rates within specific

organizations (Cartwright, 2021; Erickson et al., 2021; Jackson et al., 2023; Scholtz et al., 2014; Taylor et al., 2017). However, the five studies examining turnover data from specific organizations failed to provide evidence to demonstrate a statistical difference between individuals who participated in a TTP program and individuals who did not. Two studies lacked a control group to compare results with TTP participants (Jackson et al., 2023; Scholtz et al., 2014), and three studies did not use statistical data to compare outcomes between TTP participants and non-participants (Cartwright, 2021; Erickson et al., 2021; Taylor et al., 2017).

Program Components

Shared Components.

Didactic. Each of the TTP programs examined in this systematic review included didactic training. These ranged from four hours per month (Cartwright, 2021) to five didactic course days over one year (Scholtz et al., 2014). Content varied greatly and included topics such as mindfulness, scope of practice, critical thinking (Cartwright, 2021), role transition, billing, coding, local and national professional growth opportunities (Scholtz et al., 2014), and specialty topics (Jackson et al., 2023; Taylor et al., 2017).

Ongoing Evaluations. Ongoing evaluations were also present in each of the TTP programs evaluated. Cartwright (2021) noted the presence of quarterly evaluations conducted by trained preceptors. Erickson et al. (2021) noted that the program they assessed included regular meetings with mentors to evaluate participant progress. Jackson et al. (2023) mentioned the presence of a series of meetings with time built-in for open communication about professional milestones. Ongoing evaluations reported by Scholtz et al. (2014) appeared to be less formal and included opportunities for open communication and feedback during didactic and simulation experiences. Taylor et al. (2017) noted the presence of ongoing evaluations in the form of

feedback that was given to participants with respect to case studies and case management presentations based on patient encounters (at a rate of two per month).

Mentorship. Mentorship was also a component of each of the studies reviewed. In some cases, mentors were provided with training (Cartwright, 2021; Erickson et al., 2021) or compensation (Erickson et al., 2021). Erickson et al. (2021) reported that mentors were tasked with meeting weekly with new hires to review their self-assessments, charts and goals, to facilitate clinical experiences, and evaluate participant progress. Jackson et al. (2023) reported that mentors met with participants once a month to provide support and an outlet for open discussion. Scholtz et al. (2014) stated that mentorship was a core part of the program goals, however no mention of mentorship was made with reference to a specific program requirement. Taylor et al. (2017) also noted that mentoring was a part of the TTP program they evaluated, but few details were provided beyond reporting the existence of this component.

Common Components.

Specialty Training. Specialty training was present in four of the studies reviewed. Cartwright (2021) provided mentors to help new APRNs progress in their clinical specialty. Erickson et al. (2021) reported on the development of an adult-geriatric acute care certification program to ensure participants had proper training. Jackson et al. (2023) reported that participants in their program were involved with clinical rotations focused on oncological subspecialty training. Taylor et al. (2017) focused on specialty fellowship tracks including discipline-specific education, mentoring, and training.

Professional Development. Professional development activities were common to three of the organizations in the studies reviewed. Cartwright (2021) documented professional development through didactic classes with content focusing on accountability, nursing ethics, QI,

and library skills. Scholtz et al. (2014) noted the presence of professional development through didactic experiences including a day devoted to practice evaluation, billing, documentation, and coding. Another day was related to the provision of local and national professional growth opportunities. Taylor et al. (2017) described professional development including professional shadowing. Moreover, individuals were encouraged to join professional organizations, were taught political advocacy skills, and met with key organizational leaders for professional advice.

Components Present in Two Studies.

Several TTP components were present in two studies including a focus on wellness, QI projects, simulations, escalating case complexity, the use of participant feedback for program improvement, and monetary incentives. A focus on wellness was present in the program studied by Cartwright (2021) which included education from a certified mindfulness instructor. Jackson et al. (2023) also promoted wellness through interventions focused on well-being. Quality improvement projects were noted by Cartwright (2021) who mentioned that each fellow developed and presented a QI project guided by their leadership team. Taylor et al. (2017) also noted the presence of QI projects based on department needs. Clinical simulations were provided to participants in two of the programs discussed in this review. Scholtz et al. (2014) reported the presence of skill-based and critical thinking simulations. Taylor et al. (2017) noted simulation training that occurred for some of their specialty tracks. Escalating case complexity (and workload) was described in the study by Erickson et al. (2021). Similarly, Jackson et al. (2023) noted that program participants started with reduced capacity and select patients to ensure manageable caseloads. Use of participant feedback to facilitate program improvement was present in the program studied by Jackson et al. (2023). Scholtz et al. (2014) also noted the use of participant feedback on an ongoing basis to adjust the format and structure of the program.

Monetary incentives were present in Erickson et al.'s (2021) study where it was noted that mentors received two hours of "dedicated time" or a stipend of \$500 a month for the duration of the program (one year). Taylor et al. (2017) also reported the presence of monetary incentives in the form of bonuses and a higher starting salary for participants in the fellowship program.

Discussion

Advanced practice registered nurses and CRNAs provide essential healthcare services in various settings to a large portion of the U.S. population. Thus, retaining these practitioners after they have been hired is imperative to maintaining a functional healthcare system (Barret & Wright, 2019), especially in rural or underserved areas (Park et al., 2022). Scholars have identified that the first year of anesthesia practice is fraught with stress and anxiety which may lead to increased turnover (Tracy, 2017). The same is true for APRNs, as researchers have argued that the transition from bedside nurse to advanced practice nurse can be difficult (Cartwright, 2021; McGrath et al., 2021; Scholtz et al., 2014) and full of stress which can lead to decreased job satisfaction and increase practitioners' intent to leave (Barnes et al., 2021). Although the transition from novice to experienced APRN can be difficult, healthcare organizations can make the transition easier by providing experiences designed to facilitate adaptation to the new role (Robeano et al., 2019). Crucially, few studies have evaluated how TTP experiences influence outcomes such as satisfaction and retention for APRNs. This systematic review synthesized existing literature related to TTP programs for APRNs and CRNAs with the goal of identifying specific interventions that may improve job satisfaction and intention to stay among novice practitioners.

Study Quality

Taken together, evidence from this systematic review indicated that the quality of the studies examining APRN satisfaction, retention, and TTP experiences is weak. Similar to what Speight et al. (2019) noted, this result might be due to the emerging nature of the topic under study. Overall, the studies performed poorly on questions assessing whether the study population was clearly specified and defined, whether the sample size was justified, and if potential confounding variables were accounted for. Many of the case studies included in this review lacked comparisons between clearly defined experimental and control groups which precluded definitive conclusions about the efficacy of the interventions. Further, the use of small sample sizes, in addition to studying mainly Caucasian female APRNs, limits researchers' ability to generalize to other populations. Finally, failure to control for confounding variables can affect the reliability of the results.

Transition to Practice and Job Satisfaction

Five studies from this systematic review investigated the effect of TTP programs on job satisfaction. Each of the studies reported positive associations. Considering this consensus, readers may conclude that participation in postgraduate TTP programs is beneficial to novice APRNs. However, results from this systematic review are limited because the definition of satisfaction was different across studies. For instance, satisfaction was measured as a vague construct in one study (e.g., "satisfaction in the primary nursing position," Park et al., 2022) which made it impossible to tell what nurses experienced on a more concrete level. The remaining studies used more well-defined measures of satisfaction. However, different measures or tools were utilized (MNPJSS and NNPRT) and, even when they used the same measurement tool, some researchers used it differently than others (Bryant & Parker, 2019). Because it is not

clear that the studies involved in this systematic review utilized the same definition of satisfaction, we cannot be certain that their results should be combined to deduce an overall effect.

Moreover, only two studies (Bush & Lowery, 2016; Park et al., 2022) controlled for possible confounding variables that might have had an impact on job satisfaction and, as such, the link between TTP experiences and job satisfaction may be mis-attributed. In addition, Cartwright (2021) did not use a comparison group and provided no data to support their claim of an association between the fellowship program evaluated and job satisfaction. Consequently, it is difficult to draw definitive conclusions from these studies about the impact of TTP programs on job satisfaction.

Finally, one study reported the coefficient of determination associated with their results (Bush & Lowery, 2016) and this data indicated that the association between participation in a TTP program and job satisfaction was small. Considering this, researchers and practitioners will question the practical significance of this result. Moving forward, researchers and practitioners may be interested in how much of a relative impact TTP programs make on their outcomes of interest. For example, factors that influence job satisfaction for APRNs and CRNAs include autonomy and compensation (Negrusa, Hogan, Jordan, et al., 2021). As researchers continue to study nurses' experiences, they may consider investigating the ability for TTP programs to influence job satisfaction above and beyond factors that are known to associate with this outcome.

Transition to Practice and Retention

Results from the studies included in this systematic review suggest that TTP programs may play a role in improving retention and decreasing turnover intentions for APRNs; all seven

studies reported improvement in retention/turnover intentions. However, the results are limited in their generalizability due to small sample sizes (Cartwright, 2021; Erickson et al., 2021; Jackson et al., 2023), data representing single institutions that are not specialized hospitals (Cartwright, 2021; Erickson et al., 2021; Jackson et al., 2023; Scholtz et al., 2014; Taylor et al., 2017), and a failure to differentiate between the type of APRN and years of experience (Park et al., 2022; Scholtz et al., 2014; Taylor et al., 2017).

Other limitations include a failure to report tests of significance or impact (Cartwright, 2021; Erickson et al., 2021) and lack of comparison groups to demonstrate efficacy (Barnes et al., 2023; Jackson et al., 2023; Scholtz et al., 2014; Taylor et al., 2017). Without testing for significant differences between similar groups of individuals, differences in retention between APRNs who participated in TTPs and those who did not may be due to chance or may be nonexistent. Finally, only one out of the seven studies examining retention accounted for potentially spurious relationships (Park et al., 2022). Organizations that are interested in improving retention rates may want to consider how TTP programs link to retention while measuring other factors that may be associated with this outcome. For instance, retention likely occurs in a context of employment and thus, organizational structure, scope of practice limitations, and/or differing healthcare delivery models may influence individuals' decisions to stay or leave. If organizational and contextual factors influence retention in meaningful ways, researchers may want to consider how TTP programs bolster retention in light of these factors to determine if the return-on-investment warrants TTP experiences.

Components of Transition to Practice Programs

Several TTP components were outlined in the studies reviewed and many of these were shared across organizations. For example, all programs reviewed included the presence of

didactic interventions (of varying length and content), ongoing evaluations (to provide feedback and evaluate progress), and mentorship (providing clinical support, navigating organizational goals, and providing feedback). In addition, several of the studies reported ongoing investment into new hires including specialty training and professional development.

Although several components were shared by all TTP programs, the execution of these differed widely. For instance, didactic training ranged from five daily sessions (unstated number of hours per day) in one year (Scholtz et al., 2014), to four hours per month (Cartwright, 2021), to weekly or biweekly meetings (unstated duration; Taylor et al., 2017). Relatedly, the content of these classes did not appear to be consistent across organizations. The same can be said for ongoing evaluations where some organizations outlined formal procedures for these (Erickson et al., 2021) and others reported meetings where the provision of feedback was less formal (Jackson et al., 2023; Scholtz et al., 2014). Based on the data reviewed, it was clear that most of the TTP programs designed and implemented their training in ways that were program and/or participant-specific. Considering this, organizational leaders may decide to include some of the components utilized in these studies while customizing their specific execution to organizational requirements and participants' needs.

Importantly, none of the studies reviewed linked individual TTP program components to outcomes of interest. Because the data were not collected or analyzed in a manner to link specific interventions to APRN satisfaction or retention, it is impossible to know what types of TTP experiences are more or less effective, and whether these operate individually or in combination with one another. Moreover, though rationales were provided regarding why specific interventions were chosen (based on recommendations from the COA, 2018; ANCC, 2015), the studies reviewed did little to explain why these interventions would improve satisfaction and

retention in the first place. For example, in psychology, researchers argue that three components of high-quality motivation stem from environments that promote an individual's sense of autonomy, competence, and relatedness (Deci & Ryan, 2013). However, without data on which components of these programs are beneficial and without asking participants what about these made them effective, readers are left to guess why TTP programs are beneficial and to wonder about which components are worth the investment.

Practical Implications for Nursing Leadership

Organizational leaders who are concerned with implementing TTP programs may be most interested in the components that are typically included in such programs. Overall, research indicates that effective TTP programs are organized, structured experiences that share several features including: (a) didactic training, including simulations; (b) opportunity for feedback as new hires progress through the year; (c) mentorship to build peer support and to provide opportunities to learn organizational culture; (d) escalating case complexity to ease new hires into a full workload; and (e) clinical support as new hires learn local best practices. Many of the aforementioned features overlap with what new APRNs explain as being important to their first-year experiences including mentorship, practice-based support (including continued professional education), a manageable case load, and scheduling (Goodwin et al., 2021). Certified Registered Nurse Anesthetists described similar interest in themes that include building self-confidence, having expert guidance, and receiving support from peer mentors (Tracy, 2017). Despite the similarities across TTP programs, evidence from this review indicates that individualization was apparent for specific organizations (e.g., didactic, specialty training, etc.) to the extent that the application of these features was often tailored to organizational needs. Therefore, organizations may consider these findings as representing a template that provides an overview of *what* to

include in TTP programs while adapting specific experiences to *how* new hires function in their new work environment.

In addition, organizations should measure the efficacy of their individual TTP programs to ensure these are meeting organizational goals. Although evidence from this systematic review indicates that TTP programs can help with satisfaction and retention, it is not clear that the mere presence of these programs is sufficient. Instead, and in accordance with the IOM (2018), studies emphasized the importance of feedback to adjust TTP program experiences to best suit employees' needs (Jackson et al., 2023; Scholtz et al., 2014). Moreover, organizations that implement TTP programs should measure the success of their interventions with respect to outcomes of interest. Instead of simply providing a transition experience for novice practitioners, the goal for organizations that wish to implement these should be to create TTP programs that are designed to meet specific needs while providing evidence for their efficacy (Painter et al., 2019).

According to some estimates, the costs for training postgraduate APRNs can be upwards of \$100,000 (Bush & Lowery, 2016; Moss, 2021) and more than \$150,000 for CRNAs (Mahoney et al., 2020). Adding TTP programs to these experiences may increase this cost (Erikson et al., 2021). Because there are no designated federal support monies associated with TTP programs for APRNs (Flinter & Hart, 2017), organizations will have to assign a portion of their operating budget to the endeavor. As such, prioritizing TTP experiences for new hires cannot be seen as an "add-on" to employees' current organizational workload. Instead, TTP programs should be viewed as an essential component of the new-hire experience which necessitates adequate operating expenses.

Recommendations for Future Studies

Although evidence is building to support the positive association between TTP programs, job satisfaction, and retention among APRNs, further research is needed to determine if these relationships hold among specific subpopulations of nurses. For example, this systematic review examined nine studies, and none were focused solely on CRNAs. Moving forward, researchers should focus on including a more diverse sample of APRNs and exploring the link between TTP programs, satisfaction, and retention of the CRNA population and other APRN subpopulations with high quality, rigorous studies.

In the future, researchers may also consider studying specific aspects of job satisfaction to determine which experiences are most closely linked to retention. Recall that several of the satisfaction measures were multidimensional and included facets such as autonomy, collegiality, professional growth, and benefits (Misener & Cox, 2001). If scholars can determine which components of satisfaction are most essential to retention, TTP programs could focus on developing experiences that build upon these aspects for first-year practitioners. Similarly, as research in this area continues, scholars would be wise to isolate the components of TTP programs that are most consequential to employee satisfaction and retention. Though many components can be implemented, researchers and practitioners will benefit from knowing which are essential and which are not.

Moving forward, researchers should articulate how each component of the TTP experience is best executed. For example, didactic education was a common component of the programs in this review. However, their content and implementation varied greatly. If scholars can isolate the variables that made didactic experiences satisfactory, including what duration is most effective, they could help practitioners determine how best to implement this component

for employees. A focus on interventions with attention to their specific execution may help researchers and organizational leaders determine best practices regarding their implementation.

Finally, researchers will also find it helpful to investigate potential mediators affecting satisfaction and retention to determine the mechanisms that link TTP experiences to these outcomes. As an example, scholars who study organizational motivation have found that perceptions of competence, autonomy, and relatedness are closely linked to employee satisfaction (Deci & Ryan, 2013). Relatedly, in the nursing field, researchers have argued that the success of TTP programs may be linked to an experience that provides personalization, enhanced training, and mentorship from peers (Robeano et al., 2019). If researchers can discover links to retention and satisfaction from specific TTP components, they could incorporate this knowledge when designing TTP experiences which may streamline organizations' allocation of resources and cut costs. Ultimately, understanding why TTP programs are helpful for first year APRNs (and CRNAs) may reveal new information about role transition and offer alternative avenues for organizational leaders to pursue when designing interventions to enhance satisfaction and bolster retention.

Limitations

Although significant efforts were made to ensure that no study was overlooked, it is possible that one study (or several) was not included. Moreover, with only nine studies in this systematic review, missing studies may impact the results. Another limitation includes the type of analysis applied to the studies under investigation. Without a statistical summary, the conclusions in this project are subjective and open to scrutiny. This study is also limited regarding the population represented. Demographic information from these studies indicated that data came largely from white females (Barnes, 2023; Bryant & Parker, 2019; Bush & Lowery,

2016; Moss, 2021). As such, results from this investigation may not be generalizable to other populations. Another limitation of this project is that, although this systematic review set out to examine CRNA populations, the lack of data led to a broader analysis of APRN experiences. Without proper representation, it is impossible to know if the results reported in this review apply to the original population of interest.

Conclusion

The purpose of this DNP project was to conduct a systematic review of the literature to synthesize evidence related to the effectiveness of TTP programs for APRNs, including CRNAs. This DNP scholar project also made recommendations regarding program components that are essential for successful role transition by identifying practices that support successful TTP and examining their associations with job satisfaction and retention. This DNP project was successful at synthesizing the current literature on TTP programs as well as identifying knowledge gaps that may be addressed by future researchers. Results from this project demonstrate that TTP programs share several components and indicate that these programs are positively associated with job satisfaction and retention. However, high-quality research must be performed to definitively conclude which TTP components are most effective and how these are linked to job satisfaction and retention. To achieve this goal, researchers should engage in more methodologically rigorous studies of APRN (including CRNA) role transition to provide more definitive evidence of TTP efficacy. Ultimately, research such as this is necessary to justify the cost of TTP program implementation. To disseminate the findings of the systematic review and provide recommendations for practice, this project will be submitted for publication. A manuscript in publication form is provided in this document (Appendix E).

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Appendix A

PROSPERO Registration

A systematic review examining the impact of role transition programs on job satisfaction and retention for CRNAs and APRNs.

To enable PROSPERO to focus on COVID-19 submissions, this registration record has undergone basic automated checks for eligibility and is published exactly as submitted. PROSPERO has never provided peer review, and usual checking by the PROSPERO team does not endorse content. Therefore, automatically published records should be treated as any other PROSPERO registration. Further detail is provided [here](#).

Citation

Sadeeka Al-Majid, Sarah Giron, Britainie De Garbott. A systematic review examining the impact of role transition programs on job satisfaction and retention for CRNAs and APRNs. PROSPERO 2023 CRD42023415792 Available from: https://www.crd.york.ac.uk/prospéro/display_record.php?ID=CRD42023415792

Review question

The purpose of this systematic review is to identify practices intended to support the transition into practice for novice CRNAs, including APRNs, and to investigate the association between these programs and both job satisfaction and retention.

Searches

PubMed, CINAHL, and Cochrane databases along with the American Association of Nurse Anesthetists (AANA) journal archive were accessed, without time delimitation, to identify pertinent articles published in English. Additionally, Google Scholar was searched for relevant articles published in the last five years (March 17th, 2018 to March 17th, 2023) to avoid an unmanageable number of results. Finally, the reference lists of all relevant articles were screened for additional studies. Text words contained in the abstracts and titles of the initial relevant studies provided the basis for a full search strategy in the aforementioned databases.

Types of study to be included

This systematic review placed no restrictions on the type of study design to be included.

Condition or domain being studied

What is the impact of post graduate training programs on job satisfaction and retention for CRNAs and APRNs?

Participants/population

Novice Certified Registered Nurse Anesthetists and Advanced Practice Registered Nurses

Intervention(s), exposure(s)

Inclusion criteria were peer reviewed articles, available in the English language and in full text, that examined post graduate transition to practice programs for novice CRNAs or APRNs (graduated less than five years ago or included recall studies about the transition to practice), and that examined outcomes relating to job satisfaction and/or job retention.

Comparator(s)/control

CRNAs or APRNs that were not involved in a post-graduate transition program (i.e., fellowship, residency, onboarding program etc.).

Type and method of review

Systematic review

Anticipated or actual start date

13 March 2023

Anticipated completion date

20 May 2023

Funding sources/sponsors

Not applicable

Grant number(s)

State the funder, grant or award number and the date of award

Not applicable

Conflicts of interest**Language**

English

Country

United States of America

Stage of review

Review Ongoing

Subject index terms status

Subject indexing assigned by CRD

Subject index terms

Advanced Practice Nursing; Humans; Job Satisfaction; Nurse Anesthetists; Surveys and Questionnaires

Date of registration in PROSPERO

20 April 2023

Date of first submission

10 April 2023

Stage of review at time of this submission

Stage	Started	Completed
Preliminary searches	Yes	No
Piloting of the study selection process	Yes	No
Formal screening of search results against eligibility criteria	Yes	No
Data extraction	No	No
Risk of bias (quality) assessment	No	No
Data analysis	No	No

The record owner confirms that the information they have supplied for this submission is accurate and complete and they understand that deliberate provision of inaccurate information or omission of data may be construed as scientific misconduct.

The record owner confirms that they will update the status of the review when it is completed and will add publication details in due course.

Versions

20 April 2023

20 April 2023

Appendix B

PRISMA Flow Diagram

Figure 1

PRISMA Flow Diagram

Note. Flow diagram is from Page, McKenzie, et al. (2021).

Appendix C

Table of Evidence: CRNA and APRN Transition to Practice

Table 1

Table of Evidence: CRNA and APRN Transition to Practice

Purpose/Author	Design/Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures/Tools	Program Components	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA); Novice nurse practitioner role transition scale (NNPRT) (Barnes et al., 2023)	Cross sectional survey & CFA	N = 210 (< 1 year experience, currently working as NP) 51.7% had a formal orientation. 8.6% in a residency or fellowship	Author-developed tool (37 item NNPRT Scale; 5 Factors: Organizational Alignment, Mentorship, Sense of purpose, Competence/ Confidence, Compensation)	NA	NNPRT internal consistency = 0.95. Higher mean scores for NPs with a formal orientation (4.44) compared with NPs who did not (4.21; $p = .02$). Negative significant relationship between NNPRT & turnover intention ($r = -.59, p < 0.001$). Negative, weak (Spearman Rho coefficient = .03) and nonsignificant relationship between prior RN experience and the NNPRT ($p = 0.71$).	The NNPRT is a valid and reliable tool that can be used to assess new grad NP programs (Cronbach's alpha = 0.95). Reliability coefficients: Organizational Alignment (0.88), Mentorship (0.92), Sense of Purpose (0.90), Perceived Competence and Self-confidence (0.88), and Compensation (0.89). Individuals who received formal orientation scored higher than those without ($p < .05$).
Evaluation of job satisfaction of NPs who did versus those that did not complete an NP fellowship program (Bryant & Parker, 2019)	Descriptive pilot survey	Convenience sample (online) N = 258 NPs N = 34 < 1 year N = 101 < 5 years University of Southern Indiana	MNPJSS Likert Items "44-item survey with six sub- scales: (a) intra-practice partnership/collegiality; (b) challenge/ autonomy; (c) professional, social, and community interaction; (d) professional growth; (e) time; and (f) benefits." p E16	NA	Nonsignificant differences in job satisfaction on most MNPJSS items. Individuals without fellowship experience had lower means for: sense of value (4.65), bonuses (3.16), and compensation (3.08) compared to those who did (sense of value, 5.02, $t(87.56) = -2.05, p < .05$; bonuses available, 3.94, $t(256) = -2.94, p < .01$; compensation, 3.69, $t(256) = -2.43, p < .05$).	Limitation: small sample size. Survey distributed by a person in a position of power over participants. No correction was applied to account for family-wise error rates. Authors purport it is likely that after completion of a fellowship program practitioners may feel increased preparedness for practice, confidence, and job satisfaction.

Purpose/Author	Design/Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures/Tools	Program Components	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
Postgraduate nurse practitioner education: Impact on job satisfaction (Bush & Lowery, 2016)	Descriptive survey	N = 56 Convenience sample 2 Groups (Attended 12-month post graduate education program versus not; recruited through email marketing)	MNPJSS	NA	Over 2/3 of participants did not participate in a formal post-graduate educational experience. Statistically significant differences were found between individuals with and without postgraduate education in areas related to collegiality (with = 4.33, without = 3.94; $t(252) = 2.74$, $p < .01$), autonomy (with = 4.93, without = 4.57; $t(252) = 3.19$, $p < .01$), interaction (with = 4.72, without = 4.42; $t(252) = 2.79$, $p < .01$), and growth (with = 4.38, without = 3.78; $t(252) = 3.84$, $p < .001$). Overall job satisfaction scores were higher for individuals who completed postgraduate education (mean = 200) compared to individuals who did not (mean = 183; $t(252) = 3.42$, $p < .001$).	Inconsistencies in the way that programs are labeled (e.g., sometimes fellowships, sometimes residencies). Limitation: no distinction between types of NPs. Says that costs for training postgraduate NPs can be upwards of 100k (including support and lost productivity).
Evaluation of retention and job satisfaction after implementation of a NP residency program (Cartwright, 2021)	Cohort (12 month)	N = 9 Large mid-western children's hospital (2-6 months after program completion)	MNPJSS	Didactic, quarterly evaluation, mentorship, preceptor training, specialty training, professional development, wellness, QI project	Satisfaction scores were all high, (average report = 5.07/6). Retention was high in all previous years (2015, 2016, 2017) 88-96%. It was 100% in 2018 (after implementation of the program).	Authors argue that transition programs help bridge the gap to professional practice for novice NPs through increased job satisfaction and retention. Limitations: No control group for satisfaction. No tests of significance were conducted for retention.

Purpose/Author	Design/Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures/Tools	Program Components	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
Establishing organizational support for nurse practitioner/physician assistant transition to practice programs (Erickson et al., 2021)	Cohort Pilot Program (12 months)	Transition program group N = 8 (NP & PA) Control N = 10 (NP & PA from previous year without transition program) (74 clinics & 15 hospitals across a tristate area)	Engagement survey (3rd party) Retention evaluated by turnover data Productivity: undefined	Didactic, monthly evaluation from mentors, mentorship, specialty training, escalating caseload complexity, monetary incentive for mentors, self-assessment	100% of TTP group were still employed at one year (n = 8/8), however no data were provided for the group that did not participate in a TTP program. Engagement: 15th percentile increased to 50th national percentile ranking. Organizational turnover: 14.5% decreased to 9%. Productivity: increased to 15 % at 6 months and 11.5 % at 12 months (compared to before the program).	Transition programs increased levels of retention, engagement, productivity for NPs and PAs resulting in significant cost savings for the organization (\$1.68 million annually for retention alone). Mentor decrements in productivity and new hire stipend costs offset by increase in new hire productivity. Limitations: No data provided to determine significance of improvements.
Implementing an oncology NP fellowship: Reflections and lessons learned (Jackson et al., 2023)	Cross sectional (12 months)	N = 8 (2 NPs per cohort/year; 2019-2022)	Turnover data	Didactic, evaluation for professional milestones, monthly mentorship meetings, specialty training, wellness, escalating complexity, real-time program changes based on participant feedback	100% retention since 2020.	Professional development through fellowship can increase provider confidence, well-being, and retention. Limitations: small sample size, no control group to demonstrate efficacy of program.

Purpose/Author	Design/Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures/Tools	Program Components	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
Effects of completing a postgraduate residency or fellowship program on primary care nurse practitioners' transition to practice (Park et al., 2022)	Cross sectional survey	U.S. Health Resources & Services Administration (HRSA) 2018 National Sample Survey of Registered Nurses 75,963 NP (Primary care) 21,784 NPs selected currently working.	Likert Item Survey -role perception -autonomy -collaboration -job satisfaction -intent to leave	NA	10% received post graduate training. Role perception and able to practice full expertise: Nonsignificant difference between two groups. 49% of individuals with residency training reported they were "extremely satisfied" with their primary position compared to 42% of participants who did not participate in this training. NPs who received residency or fellowship training were more satisfied compared with NPs who did not (OR=1.29; 95% CI: 1.04, 1.59; $p = .02$). Intent to leave: 57% of nurses with residency training never considered leaving their position versus 45% who did not receive training (OR = .65, 95% CI: 1.51, 0.83; $p = .001$).	Post graduate NP programs have positive effects on NPs, organizations, and patients. "Postgraduate training appears to help build confidence and mastery of the role of independent primary care provider" (p. 38). Reduced turnover has positive financial implications for healthcare organizations, especially for rural/underserved areas. Claims to be the first nationally representative study of NP with fellowship training compared to those without. Fellowship programs may improve retention, job satisfaction, competence, and confidence of new NPs.
The care model of the future: Supporting APRNs through an innovative transition to practice program (Scholtz et al., 2014)	Cohort (3-12 months) Goals: Infrastructure for role transition, ongoing mentorship, peer support, best practices and problem solving	N=108 (55 completed) NP (99), CNS (8), CNM (1) 71% Novice 29% Experienced Large academic medical center	Unreported outcomes of interest: APRN satisfaction recruitment, and retention, productivity and engagement Examined patient and family satisfaction, patient safety events.	Didactic, competency based evaluations, mentorship, professional development, clinical simulation, feedback to the program, self-assessment	Less than 2% turnover since program implementation.	APRNs value interprofessional collaboration. Limitations: Cites improved patient safety, outcomes and APRN experience but provides no supporting data. Limitations: no control group.

Purpose/Author	Design/Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures/Tools	Program Components	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
A strategic approach for development of an advanced practice workforce. From post graduate transition-to-practice programs and beyond (Taylor et al., 2017)	Cohort (12 months)	N =158 (7 Cohorts) Largest postgraduate fellowship in the U.S., Carolinas Healthcare System	No tools or data	Didactic, individual feedback, mentorship, specialty training, professional development, QI project, clinical simulations, case study presentations, hiring bonus available for program participants	Since implementation, turnover has decreased by 50% (no data provided), 27% increase in general clinical knowledge at three months. No data, but noted a significant effect on clinical knowledge and confidence. Retention: 80% chose permanent employment post completion. Speculate on improved satisfaction.	Program Goals: “education, mentoring, recruitment, satisfaction/retention, professional development, communication, clinical competency, and regulatory requirements and credentialing” (p 13.) Fellows receive stipend & benefits, retention bonus & higher starting salary. States the program was a good return on investment. Provided better integration into the hospital environment. Enhanced recruitment Shorter recruitment time = increased productivity/revenue. Limitations: no control group.

Note. NP = Nurse practitioner, PA = Physician assistant, MNPJSS = Meisner NP job satisfaction scale, QI = Quality improvement.

Appendix D

NIH Quality Assessment Tool for Observational Cohort and Cross-Sectional Studies

Table 2

NIH Quality Assessment Tool for Observational Cohort and Cross-Sectional Studies

Study	Q1- Was the research question or objective clearly stated?	Q2- Was the study population clearly specified and defined?	Q3- Was the participation rate of eligible persons at least 50%?	Q4- Were all the subjects selected or recruited from the same or similar populations?	Q5- Was a sample size justification, power description, or variance and effect estimates provided?	Q6- Were the exposures of interest measured prior to the outcomes?	Q7- Was the timeframe between exposure and outcome sufficient?	Q8- For exposures that vary, did the study examine different levels?	Q9- Were the exposure measures clearly defined, valid, reliable, consistent?	Q10- Was the exposure measured more than once over time?	Q11- Were the outcome measures clearly defined, valid, reliable, consistent?	Q12- Were assessors blinded to exposure?	Q13- Was loss to follow-up after baseline 20% or less?	Q14- Were potential confounding variable measured and accounted for?	Rating
Barnes et al., 2023	Y	Y	NA	Y	N	N	Y	NA	Y	NA	Y	NA	NA	N	6 - Fair
Bryant & Parker, 2019	Y	N	NA	Y	N	N	Y	NA	Y	NA	Y	NA	NA	N	5 - Fair
Bush & Lowery, 2016	Y	N	N	N	Y	N	Y	NA	Y	NA	Y	NA	NA	N	5 - Fair
Cartwright, 2021	Y	N	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	NA	Y	NA	Y	N	Y	N	8 - Fair
Erickson et al., 2021	N	N	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	NA	Y	NA	N	N	Y	N	6 - Fair
Jackson et al., 2023	N	N	NA	Y	N	Y	Y	NA	Y	NA	N	N	Y	N	5 - Fair
Park et al., 2022	Y	Y	NA	Y	N	N	Y	NA	Y	NA	Y	NA	NA	Y	7 - Fair
Scholtz et al., 2014	N	N	Y	Y	N	Y	N	NA	Y	NA	N	N	NA	N	4 - Poor
Taylor et al., 2017	N	N	NA	Y	N	Y	Y	NA	Y	NA	N	N	NA	N	4 - Poor
<i>Total</i>	5/9	2/9	3/9	8/9	1/9	5/9	8/9	0/9	9/9	0/9	5/9	0/9	3/9	1/9	50/126

Note. Y = Yes, N = No. NA = not applicable. Rating: Poor = 0-4/14, Fair = 5-10/14, Good = 11-14/14 questions. Average rating = 5.5/14.

Appendix E
Manuscript for Publication

Transition To Practice Program Effects on CRNA/APRN Satisfaction and Retention:
A Systematic Review

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&

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ABSTRACT

In their first year of work, Certified Registered Nurse Anesthetists (CRNAs) and other Advanced Practice Registered Nurses (APRNs) experience high levels of stress that accompany the transition to independent practice. As a result of these experiences, CRNAs may suffer from lower levels of job satisfaction and an increased likelihood of leaving their jobs within the first year. Retaining anesthesia providers is of paramount importance to healthcare organizations that wish to reduce operating costs and maintain patient access to care. To enhance job satisfaction and retention, scholars argue that new graduates may need help transitioning into the workforce through transition to practice (TTP) programs. In the literature, multiple programs have been described with varying degrees of success. The purpose of this systematic review of the literature was to synthesize evidence related to the effectiveness of TTP programs and to determine which programmatic components are frequently included. Nine studies met inclusion criteria in this systematic review. Results indicated that TTP programs are associated with increased job satisfaction and retention for APRNs, and typically include components such as mentorship, didactic training, and ongoing evaluation. Findings are discussed regarding the strength of these relationships and directions for future research.

Keywords: Systematic Review, Transition to Practice (TTP), Fellowship, Advanced Practice Registered Nurse (APRN), Certified Registered Nurse Anesthetist (CRNA), Job Satisfaction, Retention

As novice Certified Registered Nurse Anesthetists (CRNAs) and Advanced Practice Registered Nurses (APRNs) transition into independent practitioners after graduation, they experience psychological challenges that may decrease their job satisfaction and increase the likelihood that they leave their jobs within the first year (Barnes, 2015; Barnes et al., 2021, 2023). Organizations with high turnover rates suffer from the increased financial burden of training new staff and overworking existing staff which may impact their ability to meet the healthcare needs of the communities they serve (Barret & Wright, 2019). Transition to practice (TTP) programs that provide support for novice APRNs and facilitate their acculturation into the workforce have been shown to successfully increase job satisfaction (Barnes et al., 2023; Bryant & Parker, 2019; Bush & Lowery, 2016; Cartwright, 2021; Park et al., 2022) and decrease rates of turnover (Barnes et al., 2023; Erickson et al., 2021; Jackson et al., 2023; Park et al., 2022) among advanced practice nurses.

Literature indicates that a promising strategy for improving satisfaction and retention for advanced practice nurses is the implementation of formal postgraduate TTP programs (e.g., orientation, fellowship, residency etc.) where, after graduating, individuals are trained to develop the skills and confidence to practice on their own (Urbanowicz, 2019; Windey & Cullen, 2018). APRNs who are a part of TTP programs are more likely to report successful role transition experiences and that these positive experiences are associated with significantly lower turnover intentions (Barnes et al., 2023). Despite the call to create structured TTP programs (IOM, 2011), new CRNA graduates identify a lack of these opportunities as a problem in their early practice experiences (Tracy, 2017). The same is true for APRNs, as many receive no postgraduate training and what exists is often informal (Barnes et al., 2023). Although some organizations offer postgraduate TTP programs, these often vary by organization, the structured guidelines for

their successful implementation do not yet exist, and the evidence of their impact on nursing outcomes could be stronger (Robinson, 2021; Speight et al., 2019).

Considering these issues, organizations that wish to implement such programs will benefit from recommendations based on a comprehensive, scientific synthesis of the literature. Despite the presence of another systematic review on this topic (Speight et al., 2019), the current manuscript extends this research to a larger population and includes different outcomes of interest such as retention and TTP program components. Therefore, this systematic review of the literature was conducted to synthesize evidence related to the effectiveness of TTP programs for APRNs, including CRNAs. Special attention was given to determining how these programs associate with job satisfaction and retention. Specific components (didactic education, mentorship, and specialty training, etc.) that are typically included in successful TTP programs were also examined.

Transition to Practice

The Institute of Medicine (IOM, 2011) recommends postgraduate training programs for novice APRNs to support their transition into practice with the goals of improving retention, expanding competency, and improving outcomes for patients. Literature suggests that strategies to support successful role transition include new employee orientation, onboarding, and fellowship or residency programs (Urbanowicz, 2019). Orientation is the process of becoming familiar with hospital policies, procedures, and mission statements of organizations (Garcia et al., 2017), whereas onboarding is a more organized process of longer duration (typically 30-90 days). Onboarding activities are aimed at assimilating new employees into the culture of a healthcare system (Garcia et al., 2017). Fellowships and residencies are formal and structured in design. Accredited fellowship programs follow specific program guidelines and award sub-

specialty certifications (e.g., advanced pain management for CRNAs post initial certification), typically through affiliation with a university (Council on Accreditation of Nurse Anesthesia Educational Programs [COA], 2018). Residency programs offer similar support in terms of mentorship, education, and patient care experiences, but generally do not grant sub-specialty certification (although these do often include training in specialty areas). Accredited fellowship or residency programs typically consist of comprehensive, lengthy (usually six months to one year), and individualized didactic education and clinical training (Sutor & Painter, 2020).

Transition to practice programs are relatively new for APRNs and the terms used to differentiate these experiences have not been well-defined (Firth & Marsan, 2016). Indeed, the terms *fellowship* and *residency* (along with other terms such as *orientation*, *education*, *onboarding*, and *training programs*) are often used to describe similar TTP programs in the literature. In accordance with previous research on the subject (Barnes et al., 2023), experiences that are labeled as residency, fellowship, onboarding, or orientation programs are referred to as TTP programs for the purposes of this report.

Transition to Practice Program Components

Organizations vary regarding the structural components that comprise their TTP programs. However, in the last 15 years, accrediting bodies have begun to outline standards to provide recommendations for best practice. For example, the COA (2018) requires that accredited fellowship programs employ specialized training with credentialed experts, use mentors to provide individualized guidance, and deliver regular performance evaluations. According to the COA (2018), the curriculum for post graduate fellowships must also include didactic and patient care experiences to ensure practitioner competency while meeting identified goals and objectives. Furthermore, the COA (2018) maintains that faculty and administrators

should be open to organizational program improvements based on feedback from fellowship participants.

Like CRNA populations, there are guidelines for postgraduate experiences for APRNs and RNs. The National Nurse Practitioner Residency and Fellowship Training Consortium is one such organization that provides specific guidance in their detailed accreditation standards including competency in particular workplace domains (e.g., providing appropriate referrals, utilizing telehealth, and participating in quality improvement (QI) projects). Several organizations that provide APRN TTP programs have not yet gained accreditation through the COA (or similar organizations) for these but do offer insight regarding which components are commonly included. A recent systematic review of APRN TTP programs found that these programs included several shared components such as mentorship, professional socialization activities, interprofessional training (e.g., communication with other disciplines), and direct patient care experiences (Speight et al., 2019).

Job Satisfaction

Researchers have found that newly graduated nurses face difficulties after graduation. In one study, more than half of recent APRN graduates noted that they felt unprepared and found the first year of practice to be difficult, with problems ranging from independent decision making to complex case management (MacKay et al., 2017). Similarly, Barnes et al. (2021) argued that role transitions for nurse practitioners “can be described as stressful and turbulent, leading to decreased job satisfaction and increased intent to leave” (p. 79). Satisfaction is an important variable to consider in the workplace because increased job satisfaction has been linked to retention and decreased turnover intentions for APRNs (Fasbender et al., 2019; Pasaron, 2013)

and CRNAs (Mahoney et al., 2020). Moreover, higher levels of job satisfaction among APRNs have been linked to improved patient care (Pasaron, 2013).

Research shows that APRNs who are involved with TTP programs report more satisfaction with their roles (Barnes, 2015). Considering these findings, TTP programs may prove essential to building satisfaction for new nurses. Some research findings indicate that TTP programs lead to increased job satisfaction for some APRNs, but quantitative research linking TTP, and job satisfaction is scant with respect to CRNAs. Although researchers have studied CRNAs with respect to job satisfaction (Mahoney et al., 2020; Negrusa, Hogan, Jordan, et al., 2021) as well as TTP (Tracy, 2017), few studies provide a link between these constructs. Due to the lack of quantitative research linking TTP programs to job satisfaction for CRNAs, practitioners may find it challenging to draw conclusions from the literature.

Retention

Retention refers to employees who stay employed for a period (typically between one to three years; Urbanowicz, 2019) and is measured in longitudinal studies by assessing employment status in an organization at a predetermined date. Relatedly, turnover intention reflects an individual's intent to leave an organization. Retention and turnover intentions are of concern to healthcare leadership because of the financial costs associated with the recruitment and training (Hagan & Curtis, 2018). Indeed, scholars estimate the cost of replacing one CRNA is approximately \$150,000 – a cost that may be passed on to private citizens in the form of higher healthcare costs (Mahoney et al., 2020). In addition, when employees leave their positions, an increased burden is placed on the existing workforce who struggle to absorb the added workload from staffing deficits (Barret & Wright, 2019; Fasbender et al., 2019). Nurses who work in environments that are short-staffed may be prone to making errors, providing lower quality care,

and experience decreased job satisfaction (Fasbender et al., 2019). These problems may be more salient than organizations expect considering that, in a national sample of CRNAs, 53% either left their jobs or considered leaving their jobs in a given year (Dexter et al., 2021).

Pertaining to APRNs, literature reveals that compared to individuals who did not have a formal orientation, those who received orientation scored higher on the *Novice Nurse Practitioner Role Transition (NNPRT) Scale* (Barnes et al., 2023). Importantly, scores on the NNPRT were found to be negatively associated with turnover intentions. Similar results were found in a sample of NPs with residency training who had a higher likelihood of reporting that they never considered leaving their position compared to individuals who did not receive residency training (Park et al., 2022). Other studies have been published examining the link between APRNs who participated in TTP programs and retention (Cartwright, 2021; Painter et al., 2019; Scholtz et al., 2014; Taylor et al., 2017). However, scant data exists with respect to CRNAs. Taken together, a systematic review of APRN TTP and its association with employment retention/turnover may be helpful for building confidence in the connection between these variables.

Transition to Practice Programs

Transition to practice programs are not without their drawbacks and thus implementing these without evidence of benefit may not be advisable (Speight et al., 2019). One drawback includes the potential that programs such as these may create the perception that APRNs are not ready for practice upon graduation (American Nurses Association [ANA], 2014; Speight et al., 2019). For this reason, the ANA (2014) maintains that new nurse graduates may benefit from post-graduate programs when transitioning between practice settings. However, the ANA clearly states that additional training is not necessary. A second drawback of TTP programs includes the

associated cost. Costs of postgraduate TTP programs include those required for training, and lost productivity for mentors who share their time teaching (Bush & Lowery, 2016; Goodwin et al., 2021). Other costs include time for training new hires that may come at the expense of patient access to care (Speight et al., 2019). Because there is limited public funding available to help APRNs transition into practice after graduation (Goodwin et al., 2021), organizations themselves are financially responsible for these programs. As such, the investment into TTP programs is only justified to organizations if a benefit can be demonstrated (Silvestre et al., 2017).

Although studies examining the link between TTP and both job satisfaction/and retention for APRNs exist, data from these studies have not been evaluated comprehensively to produce reliable recommendations. Moreover, much of this data comes from studies with methodological constraints that limit the confidence readers might have in their conclusions (e.g., a lack of appropriate statistical information, homogeneous populations, small sample sizes). By conducting a systematic review, this review sought to identify trends in the existing literature to provide researchers, organizations, and practitioners with a summary of data that may help build confidence regarding the associations between TTP programs, job satisfaction, and retention for APRNs.

Methods

Search Strategy

A comprehensive literature search was conducted to identify journal articles that focus on postgraduate TTP programs for novice CRNAs and APRNs. In accordance with PRISMA guidelines the assessment of records was conducted by more than one reviewer. The search was independently conducted in PubMed, OVID, CINAHL, Google Scholar and Cochrane databases and through the California State University, Fullerton (CSUF) library system, as well as the

American Association of Nurse Anesthesiology (AANA) journal archive. A time delimitation of five years (2018-2023) was applied in this search to ensure more recent results were retrieved.

The following search terms were used in various combinations; *Certified registered nurse anesthetist, CRNA, orientation, onboarding, role transition, training program, fellowship, preceptorship, satisfaction, retention, turnover, and attrition*. Due to the lack of studies retrieved involving CRNAs, a subsequent search was conducted in the same manner using the terms *Advanced Practice Registered Nurse* and *APRN* to broaden the number of results retrieved.

Articles that met inclusion criteria contained information pertaining to TTP, were peer-reviewed, available in the English language, available in full text, examined postgraduate training for novice CRNAs or APRNs (who graduated less than five years prior to measurement or included studies that asked participants to recall their experiences with TTP programs), and examined outcomes related to job satisfaction and/or job retention. Reference lists from published articles were searched to identify additional articles. One author was contacted directly for a copy of their publication. Titles and abstracts were screened for eligibility independently by two reviewers (B.D., S.A.) and disagreement was resolved by a third reviewer (S.G.).

A total of 744 articles were retrieved from databases, an additional 1,620 publications were identified through other search methods (e.g., Google Scholar, reference searching, academic journals). After duplicates ($n = 117$) and exclusions ($n = 2,195$) were removed, 52 articles were identified for closer review. Forty three articles were excluded for reasons including that they: were written in foreign language ($n = 1$), were not original research or were literature reviews ($n = 8$), lacked statistical data to draw conclusions ($n = 3$), held unrelated intervention(s) ($n = 3$), were capstone projects, master's theses, or dissertations ($n = 4$), contained unrelated outcomes ($n = 20$), or did not represent the population of interest (e.g., did not include novice

practitioners or focused on pre- as opposed to post-licensure participants; $n = 4$). The remaining nine studies were included in this review; five were located through databases and four were found through the other search methods noted above (Figure 1).

Data Extraction and Synthesis

Data was extracted in accordance with PRISMA guidelines to provide transparency (Page et al., 2021). Publication details including author(s), publication year, objectives, methodology and results (e.g., participants, setting, study design, data collection, measurement tools, outcome statistics) were manually extracted from each study and presented in tabular format (Table 1). In accordance with PRISMA guidelines, no new variables were added to the investigation while data were extracted.

Results

Overview/Study Characteristics

All studies included in this systematic review were conducted in the United States. Five studies used a cohort study design to investigate the impact of fellowship or TTP programs on outcomes of interest (Cartwright, 2021; Erickson et al., 2021; Jackson et al., 2023; Scholtz et al., 2014; Taylor et al., 2017). The remaining four studies utilized cross-sectional survey designs to investigate associations between TTP programs and outcomes of interest (Barnes et al., 2023; Bryant & Parker, 2019; Bush & Lowery, 2016; Park et al., 2022). Several types of healthcare organizations were represented in the studies including universities, a children's hospital, "for profit" and "not-for-profit" hospitals, and outpatient clinics. Of the studies that reported demographic data, more than 89% of study participants were female and more than 75% were Caucasian (Barnes et al., 2023; Bryant & Parker, 2019; Bush & Lowery, 2016; Park et al., 2022). Of the five studies that examined job satisfaction, three studies used the Misener Nurse

Practitioner Job Satisfaction Scale (MNPJSS; Bryant & Parker, 2019; Bush & Lowery, Cartwright, 2021), one created a tool (the NNPRT scale) (Barnes et al., 2023), and one used an author-created categorical scale (Park et al., 2022). Of the seven studies that reported information related to retention, five evaluated internal turnover data (Cartwright, 2021; Erickson et al., 2021; Jackson et al., 2023; Scholtz et al., 2014; Taylor et al., 2017), one used the Anticipated Turnover Scale (ATS; Barnes et al., 2021), and one used single item “yes/no” question regarding intent to leave (Park et al., 2022).

Critical Appraisal

Each article’s level of evidence was determined using the Johns Hopkins Levels of Evidence Pyramid (Dang et al., 2022). In line with current recommendations for evaluating the strength of published research, this systematic review used the Levels of Evidence Pyramid to critically appraise the quality of studies used in order to help readers ascertain the confidence they may have in the research findings (Myung, 2023). In this systematic review, five studies were determined to be Level V evidence, and four were Level III.

Quality Assessment

The National Institutes of Health (NIH) Quality Assessment Tool for Observational Cohort and Cross-Sectional Studies (National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute, 2021) was used to assess the quality of studies (Table 2). Scores were tallied based on the presence/absence of specific criteria using a series of 14 items along three dimensions including “poor” (0-4 items), “fair” (5-10 items), and “good” (11-14 items; Bagias et al., 2021). Scores for studies used in this systematic review ranged from four to eight. Taken together, the nine studies averaged a score of 5.55 out of a possible 14 points. This score represents a “fair” rating according to the NIH

quality assessment tool (Bagias et al., 2021). None of the included studies received a rating of “good.”

Transition to Practice Outcomes

Job Satisfaction

Results from the included studies indicated that TTP programs were associated with increased job satisfaction. This was true regardless of whether the MNPJSS, NNPRT or author-created tool was utilized to measure job satisfaction (Barnes et al., 2023; Bryant & Parker, 2019; Bush & Lowery, 2016; Cartwright, 2021; Barnes et al., 2023; Park et al., 2022). Bryant and Parker (2019) used individual items from the MNPJSS to study job satisfaction. However, although individuals who participated in a fellowship program reported higher satisfaction for some of the items, the majority of these results were not significant. Only one study examined APRN experiences from a cohort that had been actively enrolled in a specific TTP program (Cartwright, 2021). The other studies asked participants to reflect on their TTP experiences without regard for the type of experience or the time interval since completion. Two studies controlled for covariates to study the unique effect of TTP programs on job satisfaction. Park et al. (2022) controlled for age, sex, race, employment setting, and earnings. Bush and Lowery (2016) conducted a multiple linear regression controlling for years of APRN experience and state regulatory environment. Bush and Lowery (2016) provided data about the coefficient of determination indicating a small impact of TTP experiences on job satisfaction ($R^2 = .04$).

Retention

Seven studies examined retention measured through intent to leave and turnover data. Together, results indicated that TTP programs are associated with higher retention. Specifically, results from two studies indicate that TTP programs were associated with lower intent to leave.

One study measured intent to leave with the ATS (Barnes et al., 2023). Scores on the ATS were negatively correlated with the NNPRT ($r = -.59, p < .001$) which is associated with participation in a formal orientation program (Barnes et al., 2023). In another study, intent to leave was measured with a single item (yes/no) referring to the question: “Have you ever considered leaving the primary nursing position?” (Park et al., 2022). Results from five studies indicated that TTP programs were associated with lower turnover rates within specific organizations (Cartwright, 2021; Erickson et al., 2021; Jackson et al., 2023; Scholtz et al., 2014; Taylor et al., 2017). However, the studies examining turnover data from specific organizations failed to provide evidence to demonstrate a statistical difference between individuals who participated in TTP programs and individuals who did not. Two studies lacked a control group to compare results with TTP participants (Jackson et al., 2023; Scholtz et al., 2014), and three studies did not use statistical data to compare outcomes between TTP participants and non-participants (Cartwright, 2021; Erickson et al., 2021; Taylor et al., 2017).

Program Components

Shared Components.

Didactic. Each of the TTP programs examined included didactic training. These ranged from four hours per month (Cartwright, 2021) to five didactic days over one year (Scholtz et al., 2014). Content of the didactic training varied greatly and included topics such as mindfulness, scope of practice, critical thinking (Cartwright, 2021), role transition, billing, coding, local and national professional growth opportunities (Scholtz et al., 2014), and specialty topics (Jackson et al., 2023; Taylor et al., 2017).

Ongoing Evaluations. Ongoing evaluations were present in each of the TTP programs evaluated. Cartwright (2021) noted the presence of quarterly evaluations conducted by trained

preceptors. Erickson et al. (2021) noted regular meetings with mentors to evaluate participant progress. Jackson et al. (2023) mentioned the presence of a series of meetings with time built-in for open communication about professional milestones. Ongoing evaluations reported by Scholtz et al. (2014) appeared to be less formal and included opportunities for open communication and feedback during didactic and simulation experiences. Taylor et al. (2017) noted ongoing evaluations in the form of feedback that was given to participants with respect to case studies and case management presentations based on patient encounters (at a rate of two per month).

Mentorship. Mentorship was a component the studies reviewed. In some cases, mentors were provided with training (Cartwright, 2021; Erickson et al., 2021) or compensation (Erickson et al., 2021). Erickson et al. (2021) reported that mentors were tasked with meeting with new hires weekly to review their self-assessments, charts and goals, to facilitate clinical experiences, and evaluate participant progress. Jackson et al. (2023) reported that mentors met with participants once a month to provide support and an outlet for open discussion. Scholtz et al. (2014) stated that mentorship was a core part of the program goals, however no mention of mentorship was made with reference to a specific program requirement. Taylor et al. (2017) also noted that mentoring was a part of the TTP program they evaluated, but minimal details were provided.

Common Components.

Specialty Training. Specialty training was present in four of the studies reviewed. Cartwright (2021) provided mentors to help new APRNs progress in their clinical specialty. Erickson et al. (2021) reported the development of an adult-geriatric acute care certification program to ensure participants had proper training. Jackson et al. (2023) reported that participants in their program were involved with clinical rotations focused on oncological

subspecialty training. Taylor et al. (2017) reported specialty fellowship tracks including discipline-specific education, mentoring, and training.

Professional Development. Professional development activities were common to three of the organizations in the studies reviewed. Cartwright (2021) documented professional development through classes with content focusing on accountability, nursing ethics, QI, and library skills. Scholtz et al. (2014) noted the presence of professional development through experiences including a day devoted to practice evaluation, billing, documentation, and coding. Another day was devoted to the provision of local and national professional growth opportunities. Taylor et al. (2017) described professional development including professional shadowing. Moreover, individuals were encouraged to join professional organizations, were taught political advocacy skills, and met with key organizational leaders for professional advice.

Components Present in Two Studies.

Several TTP components were present in two studies. A focus on wellness was present in the program studied by Cartwright (2021) which included education from a certified mindfulness instructor. Jackson et al. (2023) also promoted wellness through interventions (unspecified) focused on well-being. Quality improvement projects were noted by Cartwright (2021) who mentioned that each fellow developed and presented a QI project guided by their leadership team. Taylor et al. (2017) also noted the presence of QI projects based on department needs. Clinical simulations were provided to participants in two of the programs analyzed in this review. Scholtz et al. (2014) reported the presence of skill-based and critical thinking simulations. Taylor et al. (2017) noted simulation training that occurred for some of their specialty tracks. Escalating case complexity (and workload) was described in the study by Erickson et al. (2021). Similarly, Jackson et al. (2023) noted that program participants started

with reduced capacity and select patients to ensure manageable caseloads. Use of participant feedback to facilitate program improvement was also noted. Jackson et al. (2023) included feedback in their program and Scholtz et al. (2014) also utilized participant feedback on an ongoing basis to adjust the format and structure of the program. Monetary incentives were present in Erickson et al.'s (2021) study where it was noted that mentors received two hours of “dedicated time” or a stipend of \$500 a month for the duration of the program (one year). Taylor et al. (2017) also reported the presence of monetary incentives in the form of bonuses and a higher starting salary for participants in the fellowship program.

Discussion

Quality of Evidence

Taken together, evidence from this systematic review indicate that the quality of the studies examining APRN satisfaction, retention, and TTP experiences is weak. Similar to what Speight et al. (2019) noted, this result might be due to the emerging nature of the topic under study. Overall, the studies performed poorly when assessing whether the study population was clearly specified and defined, whether the sample size was justified, and if potential confounding variables were accounted for. Many of the case studies lacked comparisons between clearly defined experimental and control groups which precluded definitive conclusions about the efficacy of the interventions. Further, the use of small sample sizes, in addition to homogenous study populations (primarily Caucasian female APRNs), limits researchers ability to generalize the findings to other APRN and CRNA populations. Finally, failure to control for confounding variables could have affected the reliability of the results.

Transition to Practice and Job Satisfaction

Five studies from this systematic review investigated the effect of TTP programs on job satisfaction: each reported positive associations. Considering this consensus, readers may conclude that participation in postgraduate TTP programs is beneficial. However, results from this systematic review are limited because the definition of satisfaction was different across studies. For instance, satisfaction was measured as a vague construct in one study (e.g., “satisfaction in the primary nursing position,” Park et al., 2022) which made it difficult to determine what nurses experienced on a more concrete level. The remaining studies used more well-defined measures of satisfaction. However, different satisfaction tools were utilized across studies (MNPJSS and NNPRT). Even when studies used the same measurement tool, some researchers used it differently than others (e.g., Bryant & Parker, 2019). Because it is not clear that the studies involved in this systematic review utilized the same definition of satisfaction, we cannot be certain that their results should be combined to deduce an overall effect. Moreover, only two studies (Bush & Lowery, 2016; Park et al., 2022) controlled for possible confounding variables that might have had an impact on job satisfaction and, as such, the link between TTP experiences and job satisfaction may be mis-attributed. In addition, Cartwright (2021) did not use a comparison group and provided no data to support their claim of an association between the fellowship program evaluated and job satisfaction. Consequently, it is difficult to draw definitive conclusions from these studies about the impact of TTP programs on job satisfaction.

Importantly, one study reported the coefficient of determination associated with their results (Bush & Lowery, 2016). This data indicated that the association between participation in a TTP program and job satisfaction was small. Considering this, researchers and practitioners should question the practical significance of this result. Moving forward, researchers and

practitioners may be interested in how much of a relative impact TTP programs make on their outcomes of interest. As researchers continue to study nurses' experiences, they may consider investigating the ability for TTP programs to influence job satisfaction above and beyond factors that are already known to be associated with this outcome.

Transition to Practice and Retention

Results from the studies included in this systematic review suggest that TTP programs may play a role in improving retention and decreasing turnover intentions for APRNs: all seven studies reported improvement in retention/turnover intentions. However, the results are limited in their generalizability due to small sample sizes (Cartwright, 2021; Erickson et al., 2021; Jackson et al., 2023), data representing single institutions that are not specialized hospitals (Cartwright, 2021; Erickson et al., 2021; Jackson et al., 2023; Scholtz et al., 2014; Taylor et al., 2017), and a failure to differentiate between the type of APRN and years of experience (Park et al., 2022; Scholtz et al., 2014; Taylor et al., 2017). Other limitations include a failure to report tests of significance or impact (Cartwright, 2021; Erickson et al., 2021) and lack of comparison groups to demonstrate efficacy (Barnes et al., 2023; Jackson et al., 2023; Scholtz et al., 2014; Taylor et al., 2017). Without testing for significant differences between similar groups of individuals, differences in retention between APRNs who participated in TTPs and those who did not may be due to chance or may be nonexistent. Finally, only one out of the seven studies examining retention accounted for potentially spurious relationships (Park et al., 2022). Organizations that are interested in improving retention rates may want to consider how TTP programs link to retention while measuring other factors that may be associated with this outcome (e.g., scope of practice limitations, healthcare delivery models, etc.).

Components of Transition to Practice Programs

Several TTP components were outlined in the studies reviewed and many of these were shared. For example, all programs reviewed included the presence of didactic interventions (of varying length and content), ongoing evaluations (to provide feedback and evaluate progress), and mentorship (providing clinical support, navigating organizational goals, and providing feedback). In addition, several of the studies reported ongoing investment into new hires including specialty training and professional development.

Although several components were shared by all TTP programs, the execution of these components differed widely. For instance, didactic training ranged from five daily sessions (unstated number of hours per day) in one year (Scholtz et al., 2014), to four hours per month (Cartwright, 2021), to weekly or biweekly meetings (also of unstated duration; Taylor et al., 2017). Relatedly, the content of these classes did not appear to be consistent across organizations. Similarly, differences for ongoing evaluations existed in the examined studies as well; some organizations outlined formal procedures for these evaluations (Erickson et al., 2021) and others reported meetings where the provision of feedback was less formal (Jackson et al., 2023; Scholtz et al., 2014). Based on the data reviewed, it is clear that most of the TTP programs designed and implemented their training in ways that were program and/or participant-specific. Considering this, organizational leaders may decide to include some of the components utilized in these studies while customizing their specific execution to organizational requirements and participants' needs.

Crucially, none of the studies reviewed linked individual TTP program components to outcomes of interest. Because the data were not collected or analyzed in a manner conducive to correlating specific interventions to APRN satisfaction or retention, it is impossible to know

what types of TTP experiences are effective. Moreover, determining whether the interventions operate individually or in combination with one another is another possible goal for future studies. Finally, though rationales were provided regarding why specific interventions were chosen, the studies reviewed did little to explain why these interventions would improve satisfaction and retention of APRNs.

Practical Implications for Nursing Leadership

Organizational leaders who are concerned with implementing TTP programs may be most interested in the components that are typically included. Generally, research indicates that effective TTP programs are organized, structured experiences that share several features including: (a) didactic training, including simulations; (b) opportunity for feedback as new hires progress through the year; (c) mentorship to build peer support and to provide opportunities to learn organizational culture; (d) escalating case complexity to ease new hires into a full workload; and (e) clinical support as new hires learn local best practices. Many of these TTP components overlap with what new APRNs describe as being important to their first-year experiences. For example, mentorship, practice-based support (including continued professional education), a manageable case load, and scheduling are all reported (Goodwin et al., 2021). Certified Registered Nurse Anesthetists described similar interest in themes that include building self-confidence, having expert guidance, and receiving support from peer mentors (Tracy, 2017). Despite the similarities across TTP programs, evidence from this review indicates that individualization was apparent for specific organizations (e.g., didactic, specialty training, etc.) as these features were often tailored to organizational needs. Therefore, organizations may consider these findings a template that provides an overview of *what* to include in TTP programs while adapting specific experiences to *how* new hires function in their new work environment.

In addition, organizations should measure the efficacy of their individual TTP programs to ensure their programs are meeting organizational goals. Although evidence from this systematic review indicates that TTP programs can help with APRN satisfaction and retention, it is not clear that the mere presence of these programs is sufficient. Instead, and in accordance with the IOM (2018), studies emphasize the importance of participant feedback to adjust TTP program experiences to best suit employees' needs (Jackson et al., 2023; Scholtz et al., 2014). Moreover, organizations that implement TTP programs should measure the success of their interventions with respect to outcomes of interest. Instead of simply providing a transition experience for novice practitioners, the goal for organizations that wish to implement these programs should be to create TTP experiences that are designed to meet specific needs while providing evidence for their efficacy (Painter et al., 2019).

According to some estimates, the costs for training postgraduate APRNs can be upwards of \$100,000 (Bush & Lowery, 2016; Moss, 2021) and more than \$150,000 for CRNAs (Mahoney et al., 2020). Adding TTP programs to novice practitioner employment experiences may increase this cost (Erikson et al., 2021). Because there are no designated federal support monies associated with TTP programs for APRNs (Flinter & Hart, 2017), organizations will have to assign a portion of their operating budget to the endeavor. As such, prioritizing TTP experiences for new hires cannot be seen as an "add-on" to employees' current organizational workload. Instead, TTP programs should be viewed as an essential component of the new-hire experience which necessitates adequate operating expenses.

Limitations

Although significant efforts were made to ensure no study was overlooked, it is possible that one (or several) publication(s) were not included. With nine studies in this systematic

review, failure to capture even one study may impact the results. Another limitation of this study includes the type of analysis applied to the studies under investigation. Without a statistical summary, the conclusions in this project are subjective and open to scrutiny.

This systematic review is also limited because demographic information from the included studies indicate that the populations of study were primarily white females (Barnes, 2023; Bryant & Parker, 2019; Bush & Lowery, 2016; Moss, 2021). As such, results from this investigation may not be generalizable to other populations. Although this systematic review set out to examine CRNA populations, the lack of data led to a broader analysis of APRN experiences. Without proper representation, it is impossible to know if the results reported in this review apply to the original population of interest.

Conclusion

Results from this project demonstrate that TTP programs share several components and indicate that these programs are positively associated with job satisfaction and retention. However, high-quality research must be performed to definitively conclude which TTP components are most effective and how these are linked to APRN and CRNA job satisfaction and retention. To achieve this goal, researchers should engage in more methodologically rigorous studies of APRN and CRNA role transition as it would provide more definitive evidence of TTP efficacy. Ultimately, research such as this is necessary to justify the cost of TTP program implementation and highlight which components are most effective for the APRN population of interest.

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Table 1: CRNA and APRN Transition to Practice

Purpose/Author	Design/Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures/Tools	Program Components	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA); Novice nurse practitioner role transition scale (NNPRT) (Barnes et al., 2023)	Cross sectional survey & CFA	N = 210 (< 1 year experience, currently working as NP) 51.7% had a formal orientation. 8.6% in a residency or fellowship	Author-developed tool (37 item NNPRT Scale; 5 Factors: Organizational Alignment, Mentorship, Sense of purpose, Competence/ Confidence, Compensation)	NA	NNPRT internal consistency = 0.95. Higher mean scores for respondents that received a formal orientation process (4.44) compared with NPs who did not (4.21; $p = .02$). Negative moderate and significant relationship between NNPRT & turnover intention ($r = -.59, p < 0.001$). Negative, weak (Spearman Rho coefficient = .03) and nonsignificant relationship between prior RN experience and the NNPRT ($p = 0.71$).	The NNPRT is a valid and reliable tool that can be used to assess new grad NP programs (Cronbach's alpha = 0.95). Reliability coefficients: Organizational Alignment (0.88), Mentorship (0.92), Sense of Purpose (0.90), Perceived Competence and Self-confidence (0.88), and Compensation (0.89). Individuals who received formal orientation scored higher than those without ($p < .05$).
Evaluation of job satisfaction of NPs who did versus those that did not complete an NP fellowship program (Bryant & Parker, 2019)	Descriptive pilot survey	Convenience sample (online) N = 258 NPs N = 34 < 1 year N = 101 < 5 years University of Southern Indiana	MNPJSS Likert Items "44-item survey with six sub- scales: (a) intra-practice partnership/collegiality; (b) challenge/ autonomy; (c) professional, social, and community interaction; (d) professional growth; (e) time; and (f) benefits." p E16	NA	Nonsignificant differences in job satisfaction on the majority of MNPJSS items. However, individuals who did not participate in a fellowship program had lower means for: sense of value (4.65), bonuses (3.16), and compensation (3.08) compared to participants who did (sense of value, 5.02, $t(87.56) = -2.05, p < .05$; bonuses available, 3.94, $t(256) = -2.94, p < .01$; compensation, 3.69, $t(256) = -2.43, p < .05$).	Limitation: small sample size. Survey distributed by a person in a position of power over participants. No correction was applied to account for family-wise error rates. Authors purport it is likely that after completion of a fellowship program practitioners may feel increased preparedness for practice, confidence, and job satisfaction.

Purpose/Author	Design/Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures/Tools	Program Components	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
Postgraduate nurse practitioner education: Impact on job satisfaction (Bush & Lowery, 2016)	Descriptive survey	N = 56 Convenience sample 2 Groups (Attended 12-month post graduate education program versus not; recruited through email marketing)	MNPJSS	NA	Over 2/3 of participants did not participate in a formal post-graduate educational experience. Statistically significant differences were found between individuals with and without postgraduate education in areas related to collegiality (with = 4.33, without = 3.94; $t(252) = 2.74$, $p < .01$), autonomy (with = 4.93, without = 4.57; $t(252) = 3.19$, $p < .01$), interaction (with = 4.72, without = 4.42; $t(252) = 2.79$, $p < .01$), and growth (with = 4.38, without = 3.78; $t(252) = 3.84$, $p < .001$). Overall job satisfaction scores were higher for individuals who completed postgraduate education (mean = 200) compared to individuals who did not (mean = 183; $t(252) = 3.42$, $p < .001$).	Inconsistencies in the way that programs are labeled (e.g., sometimes fellowships, sometimes residencies). Limitation: no distinction between types of NPs. Says that costs for training postgraduate NPs can be upwards of 100k (including support and lost productivity).
Evaluation of retention and job satisfaction after implementation of a NP residency program (Cartwright, 2021)	Cohort (12 month)	N = 9 Large mid-western children's hospital (2-6 months after program completion)	MNPJSS	Didactic, quarterly evaluation, mentorship, preceptor training, specialty training, professional development, wellness, QI project	Satisfaction scores were all high, (average report = 5.07/6). Retention was high in all previous years (2015, 2016, 2017) 88-96%. It was 100% in 2018 (after implementation of the program).	Authors argue that transition programs help bridge the gap to professional practice for novice NPs through increased job satisfaction and retention. Limitations: No control group for satisfaction. No tests of significance were conducted for retention.

Purpose/Author	Design/Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures/Tools	Program Components	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
<p>Establishing organizational support for nurse practitioner/physician assistant transition to practice programs (Erickson et al., 2021)</p>	<p>Cohort Pilot Program (12 months)</p>	<p>Transition program group N = 8 (NP & PA)</p> <p>Control N = 10 (NP & PA from previous year without transition program)</p> <p>(74 clinics & 15 hospitals across a tristate area)</p>	<p>Engagement survey (3rd party)</p> <p>Retention evaluated by turnover data</p> <p>Productivity: undefined</p>	<p>Didactic, monthly evaluation from mentors, mentorship, specialty training, escalating caseload complexity, monetary incentive for mentors, self-assessment</p>	<p>100% of TTP group were still employed at one year (n = 8/8), however no data were provided for the group that did not participate in a TTP program.</p> <p>Engagement: 15th percentile increased to 50th national percentile ranking.</p> <p>Organizational turnover: 14.5% decreased to 9%.</p> <p>Productivity: increased to 15 % at 6 months and 11.5 % at 12 months (compared to before the program).</p>	<p>Transition programs increased levels of retention, engagement, productivity for NPs and PAs resulting in significant cost savings for the organization (\$1.68 million annually for retention alone).</p> <p>Mentor decrements in productivity and new hire stipend costs offset by increase in new hire productivity.</p> <p>Limitations: No data provided to determine significance of improvements.</p>
<p>Implementing an oncology NP fellowship: Reflections and lessons learned (Jackson et al., 2023)</p>	<p>Cross sectional (12 months)</p>	<p>N = 8</p> <p>(2 NPs per cohort/year; 2019-2022)</p>	<p>Turnover data</p>	<p>Didactic, evaluation for professional milestones, monthly mentorship meetings, specialty training, wellness, escalating complexity, real-time program changes based on participant feedback</p>	<p>100% retention since 2020.</p>	<p>Professional development through fellowship can increase provider confidence, well-being, and retention.</p> <p>Limitations: small sample size, no control group to demonstrate efficacy of program.</p>

Purpose/Author	Design/Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures/Tools	Program Components	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
<p>Effects of completing a postgraduate residency or fellowship program on primary care nurse practitioners' transition to practice (Park et al., 2022)</p>	<p>Cross sectional survey</p>	<p>U.S. Health Resources & Services Administration (HRSA) 2018 National Sample Survey of Registered Nurses 75,963 NP (Primary care) 21,784 NPs selected currently working.</p>	<p>Likert Item Survey -role perception -autonomy -collaboration -job satisfaction -intent to leave</p>	<p>NA</p>	<p>10% received post graduate training. Role perception and able to practice full expertise: Nonsignificant difference between two groups. 49% of individuals with residency training reported they were "extremely satisfied" with their primary position compared to 42% of participants who did not participate in this training. NPs who received residency or fellowship training were more satisfied compared with NPs who did not (OR=1.29; 95% CI: 1.04, 1.59; $p = .02$). Intent to leave: 57% of nurses with residency training never considered leaving their position versus 45% who did not receive training (OR = .65, 95% CI: 1.51, 0.83; $p = .001$).</p>	<p>Post graduate NP programs have positive effects on NPs, organizations, and patients. "Postgraduate training appears to help build confidence and mastery of the role of independent primary care provider" (p. 38). Reduced turnover has positive financial implications for healthcare organizations, especially for rural/underserved areas. Claims to be the first nationally representative study of NP with fellowship training compared to those without. Fellowship programs may improve retention, job satisfaction, competence, and confidence of new NPs.</p>
<p>The care model of the future: Supporting APRNs through an innovative transition to practice program (Scholtz et al., 2014)</p>	<p>Cohort (3-12 months) Goals: Infrastructure for role transition, ongoing mentorship, peer support, best practices and problem solving</p>	<p>N=108 (55 completed) NP (99), CNS (8), CNM (1) 71% Novice 29% Experienced Large academic medical center</p>	<p>Unreported outcomes of interest: APRN satisfaction recruitment, and retention, productivity and engagement Examined patient and family satisfaction, patient safety events.</p>	<p>Didactic, competency based evaluations, mentorship, professional development, clinical simulation, feedback to the program, self-assessment</p>	<p>Less than 2% turnover since program implementation.</p>	<p>APRNs value interprofessional collaboration. Limitations: Cites improved patient safety, outcomes and APRN experience but provides no supporting data. Limitations: no control group.</p>

Purpose/Author	Design/Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures/Tools	Program Components	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
<p>A strategic approach for development of an advanced practice workforce. From post graduate transition-to-practice programs and beyond (Taylor et al., 2017)</p>	<p>Cohort (12 months)</p>	<p>N =158 (7 Cohorts)</p> <p>Largest postgraduate fellowship in the U.S., Carolinas Healthcare System</p>	<p>No tools or data</p>	<p>Didactic, individual feedback, mentorship, specialty training, professional development, QI project, clinical simulations, case study presentations, hiring bonus available for program participants</p>	<p>Since implementation, turnover has decreased by 50% (no data provided), 27% increase in general clinical knowledge at three months.</p> <p>No data, but noted a significant effect on clinical knowledge and confidence.</p> <p>Retention: 80% chose permanent employment post completion.</p> <p>Speculate on improved satisfaction.</p>	<p>Program Goals: “education, mentoring, recruitment, satisfaction/retention, professional development, communication, clinical competency, and regulatory requirements and credentialing” (p 13.)</p> <p>Fellows receive stipend & benefits, retention bonus & higher starting salary.</p> <p>States the program was a good return on investment.</p> <p>Provided better integration into the hospital environment.</p> <p>Enhanced recruitment Shorter recruitment time = increased productivity/revenue.</p> <p>Limitations: no control group.</p>

Note. NP = Nurse practitioner, PA = Physician assistant, MNPJSS = Meisner NP job satisfaction scale, QI = Quality improvement.

Table 2: NIH Quality Assessment Tool for Observational Cohort and Cross-Sectional Studies

Study	Q1- Was the research question or objective clearly stated?	Q2- Was the study population clearly specified and defined?	Q3- Was the participation rate of eligible persons at least 50%?	Q4- Were all the subjects selected or recruited from the same or similar populations?	Q5- Was a sample size justification, power description, or variance and effect estimates provided?	Q6- Were the exposures of interest measured prior to the outcomes?	Q7- Was the timeframe between exposure and outcome sufficient?	Q8- For exposures that vary, did the study examine different levels?	Q9- Were the exposure measures clearly defined, valid, reliable, consistent?	Q10- Was the exposure measured more than once over time?	Q11- Were the outcome measures clearly defined, valid, reliable, consistent?	Q12- Were assessors blinded to exposure?	Q13- Was loss to follow-up after baseline 20% or less?	Q14- Were potential confounding variable measured and accounted for?	Rating
Barnes et al., 2023	Y	Y	NA	Y	N	N	Y	NA	Y	NA	Y	NA	NA	N	6 - Fair
Bryant & Parker, 2019	Y	N	NA	Y	N	N	Y	NA	Y	NA	Y	NA	NA	N	5 - Fair
Bush & Lowery, 2016	Y	N	N	N	Y	N	Y	NA	Y	NA	Y	NA	NA	N	5 - Fair
Cartwright, 2021	Y	N	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	NA	Y	NA	Y	N	Y	N	8 - Fair
Erickson et al., 2021	N	N	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	NA	Y	NA	N	N	Y	N	6 - Fair
Jackson et al., 2023	N	N	NA	Y	N	Y	Y	NA	Y	NA	N	N	Y	N	5 - Fair
Park et al., 2022	Y	Y	NA	Y	N	N	Y	NA	Y	NA	Y	NA	NA	Y	7 - Fair
Scholtz et al., 2014	N	N	Y	Y	N	Y	N	NA	Y	NA	N	N	NA	N	4 - Poor
Taylor et al., 2017	N	N	NA	Y	N	Y	Y	NA	Y	NA	N	N	NA	N	4 - Poor
<i>Total</i>	5/9	2/9	3/9	8/9	1/9	5/9	8/9	0/9	9/9	0/9	5/9	0/9	3/9	1/9	50/126

Note. Y = Study did include this information, N = study did not include this information. NA = not applicable. Rating: Poor = 0-4/14 questions, Fair = 5-10/14 questions, Good = 11-14/14 questions. Average rating of the studies = 5.5/14.

Figure 1: PRISMA Flow Diagram

Note. Flow diagram is from Page, McKenzie, et al. (2021).